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6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

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Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-09

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication
DIS	Direct Injection System
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
MAA	Multi-Actor Approach
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
SFTs	Smart Farming Technologies
TGs	Key Target Groups
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UVP	Unique Value Proposition

Table 1: List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Executive Summary

Smart Droplets is a groundbreaking project aiming at revolutionizing crop care tasks by integrating physical and digital assets to optimize field performance and minimize environmental impact. While introducing a novel and holistic approach to crop care tasks, by combining key technological aspects in open field spraying, the project focuses on advancing both hardware and software capabilities during chemical application to meet sustainability targets.

Smart Droplets relies on several critical technological building blocks towards creating a comprehensive system capable of translating large volumes of data into meaningful information and impactful spraying commands in the field.

Aiming at unveiling the immense potential of the innovative technological approach and demonstrating the real-world impact, Smart Droplets envisages two pilots in Spain and Lithuania, chosen for their diversified and complementary environments. These pilots serve as tangible showcases, showcasing the remarkable effectiveness and scalability of Smart Droplets cutting-edge solutions.

Through the integration of autonomous robotic platforms, innovative spraying techniques, digital twin technology, and AI models, Smart Droplets aims to deliver environmental, economic, regulatory, business, scientific, and societal benefits, ultimately contributing to the attainment of the Green Deal goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction, while aligning with the objectives of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) reform.

The Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1) embodies a systematic framework meticulously designed to facilitate efficient internal information sharing within the consortium while concurrently laying out a comprehensive strategy for disseminating project insights and outcomes to the designated stakeholders. This document marks the inaugural iteration of the DEC plan and reports, serving as the foundational blueprint for subsequent refinement and implementation. Subsequent phases at M12, M24, and M42 will witness iterative updates to this strategic roadmap, enabling alignment with the evolving project landscape and facilitating a measured progression of dissemination, communication, and exploitation efforts.

The respective deliverable Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2 (D6.2) aims at:

- Establish an efficient communication framework for disseminating information to project stakeholders and pertinent actors within the project's scope, both externally and internally.
- Develop a distinctive project brand and identity to facilitate the consistent and engaging delivery of messages that captivate and sustain the attention of target audiences.
- Prompt audience engagement by identifying actionable steps that can contribute positively to the project's goals and aims.
- Put into motion a structured framework encompassing guidelines and directives to facilitate the successful exploitation and safeguarding of project outcomes, particularly concerning the commercial utilization and reuse of the services and tools crafted within the Smart Droplets project.

This document represents the subsequent rendition of the deliverable titled "Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2 (D6.2)." Over the course of the Smart Droplets project's timeline, continuous updates will be incorporated, collating insights from all project partners, as progress in communication, dissemination initiatives, and exploitation trajectories of key project outcomes are monitored. The refinement of this deliverable will culminate by encapsulating the culmination of dissemination and communication accomplishments, an assessment of their realization and influence, along with the formulation of strategies for pertinent post-project activities.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Summary

The Smart Droplets project focuses on supporting the further development of Smart Farming Technologies (SFTs) that are considered key-enablers for farmers to better monitor their crops and reduce the use of chemicals (fertilizers and plant protection products) as well as to reduce GHG emissions, to enable reaching the Green Deal targets towards reduction of agrochemicals. To this end, the Smart Droplets project introduces a novel approach for crop care tasks, by connecting key-technological aspects during open field spraying and is committed to advancing both hardware and software capabilities during chemical application, in order to meet the sustainability scope of the EU Green Deal and the recently reformed Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Smart Droplets' solution relies upon implementing the Autonomous retrofit tractors with Direct Injection System (DIS) for intelligent spraying - avoiding exposure of farmers to hazardous chemicals. Through the combination of high-level technologies (>TRL 7), Smart Droplets adopts a hybrid approach for spraying operations, combining Data/AI/Digital Farm Twin technologies designed to translate data into actionable information, and real-time data collected from Field demonstrators evaluating and demonstrating optimized technologies in the real environments. Ensuring replicability and uptake of digital technologies by deploying innovative tools, services, and recommendations while making them relevant and of practical use to farmers, advisors, and policymakers across Europe; Smart Droplets will test the solution on two diversified and complementary environments, namely apple orchard and wheat farms. Moreover, Smart Droplets Academy will run each year, engaging and educating non-experts stakeholders operating within the agricultural vertical on AI, AI ethics, Data and Agrifood Robotics. The Smart Droplets Consortium consists of all agricultural AI, data and robotics value chain actors, and is well-balanced in terms of expertise, entity type, and geographical distribution necessary to meet its objectives.

1.2. Document Scope

The Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation (DEC) plan, along with its associated reports, orchestrates a meticulous roadmap that facilitates seamless information exchange within the consortium and crafts an encompassing strategy for disseminating project insights and outcomes to the specified stakeholders. This document inaugurates its journey as the inaugural iteration, laying the foundation for the DEC plan and reports. Subsequent editions shall ensure its ongoing relevance, navigating the ebbs and flows of project execution with strategic updates at critical junctures (M12, M24, M42) to oversee its meticulous realization. It is imperative to note that this represents the second, refined iteration of the deliverable.

1.3. Document Structure

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

Chapter 1 provides a summary of the project, with the document scope and its overall structure for better comprehension and readability.

Chapter 2 provides an overview of the project's key outcomes, as well as the dissemination and communication strategy with the corresponding timeliness and target groups.

Chapter 3 dives into the specific dissemination and communication activities, tools and channels developed and to be used through the duration of the project's implementation including the visual identity, communication material, and channel mix.

Chapter 4 outlines and explains the specified reporting and monitoring procedures and tools used to track progress; namely focusing on KPIs.

Chapter 5 defines the initial entry point of the project's exploitable results while keeping in mind their detailed expansion and elaboration in deliverable D6.5 Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 in M6.

Chapter 6 presents the conclusions of the deliverable.

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Annex A presents the project's brand book.

Annex B provides the logo variations of Smart Droplets that will be used for different media.

Annex C presents Smart Droplets' social media banners that will be used on the website and social media.

Annex D provides the deliverable template.

Annex E provides the brochures that have been created to promote Smart Droplets project during partners' participation in events.

Annex F provides the 3 posters that have been developed, one for the project in a nutshell, one for the Spanish pilot and the other one for the Lithuanian pilot.

Annex G provides the factsheets that have been developed during the current reporting period.

Annex H provides the roll-up banner that partners utilise when they are representing the project.

Annex I present the wide variety of communication material that has been created.

Annex J presents the zoom background that has been design in order to promote the project during online meetings, workshops, events.

Annex K provides the template that has been used in order to create the first press release and it will be utilised again for the upcoming ones.

Annex L provides the event planning template to be used for gathering information from partners regarding the events they are already planning on attending.

Annex M provides the synergy mapping template that partners will complete with information on existing projects, networks, alliances etc., that they are currently part of and could be relevant to Smart Droplets.

Annex N provides the publication planning template that partners will complete with information on peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, any other planned publications.

Annex O provides the template of Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue.

Annex P specifies the strategic analytic tools that will be exploited during the development of the Go-to-market strategy.

Annex Q presents the Business model canvas.

2. Overview

2.1. Project Aim and Outcome

In recent years, agricultural environments are characterized by rapid changes, while **crop care** tasks have always been repetitive, tedious, and potentially hazardous exposing farmers to health risks that should be avoided. Consequently, the sector is shifting towards more selective treatment applications to improve the quality and efficiency of chemical spraying while simultaneously benefiting workers in this sector as well as the planet.

In the case of **crop spraying operations**, AI models, data, and exploitation of autonomous robotic systems have not reached a mature technological level, mainly due to the lack of a holistic approach that combines physical and digital assets for optimal field performance and minimum environmental impact. AI and Data and robotic advances on SFTs can contribute to fulfilling this ambition, bringing benefits in terms of reduced pesticide use, low carbon emissions, low water use, and reduced food waste, thus enabling environmental sustainability.

Smart Droplets' therefore aims is to advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical applications for resource optimization and minimization of chemical waste. To accomplish this vision, this project will use already existing technologies (>TRL 7) developed within but not limited to the agricultural industry.

Figure 1: Smart Droplets concept approach

The Smart Droplets consortium consists of **9** partners across **6** countries bringing together experts in **SFTs** (e.g., Direct Injection Spraying (DIS), Digital twins, data infrastructures, AI models), in **agricultural issues** (e.g., CAP, pesticide application, environmental assessment) and **social sciences** (e.g., business performance metrics, communication activities, marketing, training and capacity building).

Smart Droplets will engage a multi-actor approach and feedback-driven solution strengthening utilizing the **2** farm pilot test cases to contribute to the project's key 3 major outcomes grouped in the following dimension:

- **Innovative AI, data and robotics solution:** A mix of robotic and non-robotic components focusing on resource optimization and waste reduction when applying chemicals achieved by using state-of-the-art concepts on planning and navigation for the retrofit tractor along with AI, computer vision and process-based agronomic models.

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- **Optimised AI, data and robotics:** The use of AI-assisted techniques to teach the Digital Farm Twin with high generalization capacity across diverse weather conditions and geographic and site-specific, multi-chemical spraying system for better monitoring of sprayers efficiency and targeted crop interventions.
- **Robotics solutions in harsh environments:** Capability of the solution to localize itself in the environment properly through a 3D localization and mapping solution tailored to the challenges found in agriculture.

Figure 2: Smart Droplets timeline

2.2. Methodology

A robust DEC plan is fundamental for creating lasting impact and will provide a concrete roadmap for partners in order to boost the growth of the Smart Droplets ecosystem, raise awareness of project activities and maximize impact among key stakeholders and target groups at the broader social, policy, and industry level.

The Smart Droplets DEC plan is inspired by the **SOSTAC model**¹ which includes the following key elements: Situation analysis, Objectives, Stakeholders & Strategy, Methods & activities, Control through concrete KPIs.

Figure 3: Smart Droplets DEC methodology

¹ <https://prsmith.org/sostac/>

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- **Situation analysis:** A state-of-play analysis in which the current challenges to be addressed by the project, the consortium's expertise, the scientific, societal and economic impacts during and after the project and the potential IPR of the results are identified and explained.
- **Objectives:** The DEC plan will elaborate upon clear and measurable objectives that will be achieved through the implementation of communication, dissemination and exploitation measures.
- **Stakeholders & Strategy:** Identification of target groups and key messages for effective communication strategy.
- **Methods & Activities:** The DEC plan will build upon the activities, tools and channels defined in the proposal and include the contributions expected from partners, and their distribution over the duration of the project. Open Science practices will be factored into all aspects of DEC implementation.
- **Control:** Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) with specific targets determined during the proposal will be used to monitor the progress of the DEC implementation. Templates for partner reporting will also be used together with digital tools for record keeping, all of which will be presented in the Chapter 4.

2.2.1. Multi-actor Approach

The cornerstone of the Smart Droplets project lies in its vibrant and participatory multi-actor approach (MAA), a strategic framework that propels the project beyond conventional boundaries. This approach reflects a profound commitment to harnessing the power of collaboration and diverse expertise to drive innovation in the realm of precision agriculture. The 'multi-actor' approach is key to the interactive innovation model. Interactive innovation "stresses relations between actors and process" where the most important resources are the diverse types of knowledge and their links, and interactive learning is the most valuable process. In this context, the multi-actor approach and the way diverse actors work well together is central to effectively delivering unique, impactful results. As so, Smart droplets will use a multi-actor approach, bringing together all relevant forms of experience and knowledge from a diverse set of partners and stakeholders to appraise, gather, cocreate and disseminate practical solutions to real needs and achieve the project's aims. Interactive innovation requires a participatory 'bottom-up approach,' facilitating those at the core of the project to influence project outcomes. This is a social process rather than a 'top-down' scientific approach and also allows members to be involved in the entire development process, from decision-making to evaluation.

Figure 4: Smart Droplets stakeholder's groups

Unlike traditional methodologies, the Smart Droplets MAA isn't confined to the project's internal team; rather, it expands to encompass an extensive network of stakeholders. This network includes researchers, farmers,

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technology enthusiasts, policy makers, and local communities, all interconnected by a shared goal: to revolutionize agricultural spraying practices through technology and knowledge exchange. This approach acknowledges that each stakeholder brings a unique perspective, and by combining these perspectives, a richer tapestry of insights emerges.

Smart Droplets' MAA is characterized by several defining principles:

1. **Inclusivity and Collaboration:** The project is a stage where all stakeholders have a role to play. By inviting diverse actors into the fold, Smart Droplets catalyzes meaningful interactions that transcend traditional boundaries. This inclusive environment ensures that all voices are heard, fostering a sense of ownership and commitment to the project's success.
2. **Customization for Impact:** The approach is rooted in recognizing the varied needs and aspirations of different stakeholders. By tailoring solutions to specific contexts and challenges, Smart Droplets ensures that its innovations are not one-size-fits-all but rather attuned to the complexities of the real world.
3. **Demonstration and Application:** Smart Droplets doesn't just stop at theoretical discussions. The project thrives on "proof of concept" demonstration cases that serve as living laboratories for innovation. By collaborating with local actors, new solutions are crafted and tested, igniting a cycle of continuous improvement.
4. **Geographical Diversity:** The project's reach extends across multiple countries, each offering a unique backdrop for stakeholder engagement. This geographical diversity enriches the approach by bringing together stakeholders from diverse cultural, economic, and environmental backgrounds.
5. **Capacity Building and Learning:** Beyond the immediate project outcomes, Smart Droplets nurtures a culture of learning and empowerment. Capacity-building activities ensure that stakeholders are not just beneficiaries of innovations but active contributors to the evolving agricultural landscape.
6. **Real-world Impact:** The MAA underscores the project's commitment to generating real-world impact. By involving stakeholders across the value chain, from research to policy, Smart Droplets ensures that its innovations resonate with the industry's needs and broader societal objectives.

This dynamic approach echoes throughout every aspect of Smart Droplets. Stakeholders are invited to shape the project's course, engage in collaborative decision-making, and contribute their unique expertise. This active participation ensures that the innovations are grounded, practical, and aligned with the aspirations of those who stand to benefit most.

Furthermore, the project's multi-actor approach extends to communication and dissemination strategies. By sharing knowledge through diverse platforms, Smart Droplets fosters a community of practice that thrives on the exchange of insights and experiences.

In sum, the Smart Droplets MAA embodies the essence of interactive innovation, where the convergence of diverse perspectives fuels a collective journey toward transformative change. By embracing collaboration, customization, and a shared commitment to impact, the project sets a precedent for a more inclusive and effective approach to shaping the future of precision agriculture.

2.2.2. Key Scenarios

The process of interactive innovation followed by Smart Droplets, will involve a series of specific scenarios and tools (based upon the LIAISON project Practitioner Handbook²) which have been identified to ensure interactive innovation and the multi-actor approach are utilized during the project implementation, shown in the figure below. These range from engaging and incentivising actors/stakeholders to become involved, to co-creation, to applying new knowledge on the ground.

² <https://liaison2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/LIAISON-Assessment-Tools.pdf>

Figure 5: Key scenarios in multi-actor approach

For each of the above mentioned 6 key scenarios, relevant tools have been identified while some of them have already been tested during the proposal stage:

Scenario 1: ENGAGING

Tool: STAKEHOLDERS PRIORITISATION

The tool is used for the prioritisation of the identified stakeholders' groups assessing the types of actors involved in the multi-actor approach. The prioritisation has already been made by the project partners during the proposal and team-building phase and it was based on the specific needs that Smart Droplets aims to address. An assessment of the strengths and weaknesses of each of the stakeholders' groups was also made. The specific order of this prioritisation process is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Prioritisation of stakeholders

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Personas³ are another tool that could be used to gain a better understanding of stakeholders and registering their needs with services design methods in order to strengthen stakeholder engagement.

Scenario 2: EXAMINING

Tool: JOURNEY MAPPING

The tool is used for understanding the experiences and knowledge of the stakeholders within the project, identifying impacts of the project and their subjective evaluations of the project. The tool intends to assess the extent to which the stakeholder's experiences match with what the project envisaged and intended, pinpointing particular events and experiences. Journey mapping tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 3: CREATING

Tool: GROUND RULES: IDENTIFICATION OF OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF AGREEMENT-BASED COOPERATION

The tool is used for assessing cultural norms, held by different actors involved in multi-actor work, that should be respected in the interactive innovation process to enhance how the potential of a diverse group is realised. The tool has been used during project development stage, but it can be used iteratively throughout the interactive innovation process.

Scenario 4: ADDRESSING

Tool: TRIZ (Theory of Inventive Problem-Solving)

The tool is used for assessing how actors are examining challenges and opportunities in the interactive innovation process, facilitating them to look at challenges and opportunities from new perspectives as well as engage in new forms of external knowledge to fuel interactive innovation. TRIZ tool can be used throughout the project implementation.

Scenario 5: APPLYING

Tool: WHAT, WHO, WHY, WHERE, WHEN & HOW

The tool is used for planning multi-actor tasks in advance, identifying:

- Which actors & stakeholders will be involved – Who?
- The tasks they will be involved in – What?
- Why would they want to be involved in such tasks – Why?
- The logistics and approach of the tasks – Where? When? and
- How? The tool has been used during project development stage allowing partners to avoid fatigue, duplication and to maximise opportunities for synergies between tasks.

Scenario 6: EVALUATING

Tool: 'CAUSES AND EFFECTS': BUILDING HYPOTHESES: LINKING ACTIONS TO RESULTS

The tool is used for facilitating partners to generate hypotheses regarding the causes and effects of actions leading to actions, then to results and subsequently to objectives and breaking it down, fact-checking and proofing. It also allows participants to continuously reflect and evaluate the decision-making process regarding the choice of project actions, revising and adapting their plans. The tool will be used throughout the project implementation.

³ <https://servicedesigntools.org/tools/personas>

2.3. Specific Objectives and Time Plan

In order to provide a verifiable trajectory geared towards clear milestones and an estimated deadline the DEC plan objectives are **S.M.A.R.T** (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-Bound). The objectives below are used as the structural backbone of the DEC plan and are divided into dissemination, communication and exploitation objectives.

Dissemination Objectives

The dissemination activities are expected to diffuse the knowledge generated in the context of the project, aiming to ensure both a mid- and long-term impact. More specifically the dissemination activities will be carefully planned to ensure that the project's advancements are widely spread to the intended targeted audiences with appropriate tools and that the key stakeholders are engaged early and actively participate during each of the project's phases. Smart Droplet applies an intensive dissemination strategy that leads all the relevant actions from the very early stages of the project. The intended strategy is aligned with the below dissemination objectives:

- Bring a critical mass of stakeholders and maximize outreach opportunities for Smart Droplets with targeted messaging and customized content.
- Diffuse scientific and technological knowledge generated during Smart Droplets and put it to productive use via capacity building.
- Nurture a collaboration framework for complementarities/ synergies with projects, initiatives, and pan European networks of DIHs and capitalise on the results.
- Get feedback from key stakeholder segments and potentials users to make sure our developments are going in the right direction and iterate.
- Align and integrate dissemination, communication, community building activities with exploitation efforts to ensure sustainability of reusable assets.
- Encourage smooth exploitation of Smart Droplets solution and seamless entry to market.

Communication Objectives

All actions that contribute to the diffusion of the project's results beyond the consortium and the direct stakeholders are considered as communication activities. In essence, communication activities are focused on maximising the visibility of the project, through widely attracting a wide range of stakeholders who are invited to embrace the project's results and benefit from the project's advancements. To achieve this, attention will be paid to adapt the communication means, the measures, and the content both to the need and knowledge levels of the target groups as well as to the status, progress and needs of the Smart Droplets project. To ensure that the communication measures will effectively address the project's expectations, communication objectives have been set:

- Pair focused content marketing and community-building strategies.
- Raise awareness, facilitate information exchange and capacity building on data-driven sustainability-oriented technology innovations.
- Encourage their acceptability by farmers, their advisors, policymakers.
- Reflect gender equality and inclusivity in the approach, tools and channels.

Exploitation Objectives

The exploitation refers to the action of making use of and benefiting from project results. Hence, Smart Droplets exploitation activities are recognized as the key enabler for success of the project. All the consortium partners are committed to the exploitation of the project's results and their diverse and complementary research and business contexts provide all potential exploitation modalities and routes to bring Smart Droplets results to all targeted stakeholders (including manufacturers and system integrators, farmers, agrifood extension service providers, AI/data/robotics providers, researchers & academia, EDIH/DIHs/AI, data, robotics innovation networks, Policy makers and regulators). A combination of activities will span throughout the project duration

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and will vary in intensity, based on the amount of information that can be made available and the results that will be produced during the project's lifetime. Hence, the main goal of Smart Droplets exploitation actions is to develop an effective way to exploit all commercial and non-commercial project results during and beyond the life of the project. To that end, the Smart Droplets exploitation strategy will focus on the following objectives:

- Set the ground for the planning of exploitation related WP6 deliverables. This will require to first investigate links and dependencies between other project's WPs and tasks, as well as to capture exploitation related KPIs that should be achieved by the end of the project.
- Identify and systematically validate Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that are foreseen in the project (commercial and non-commercial) through iterative sprints - with timelines adjusted to follow the timelines of piloting activities.
- Perform a thorough market analysis to understand the market contexts, challenges, competitive landscapes, target markets and the market positioning of the commercial key exploitable results.
- Explore various funding sources from both public and private sources in order to help Smart Droplets beneficiaries to secure follow-up investment and funding that can ensure financial sustainability of their business solutions.
- Develop joint and individual exploitation plans for project partners who are foreseen to have market exploitable assets during the project's timeframe (with the focus on both organizational and financial aspects)
- Plan the main actions to be undertaken by the project's consortium in order to ensure the sustainability of the project and its findings after the end of the project (Sustainability Plan)
- Outline IPR management strategies guiding the joint and individual exploitation capabilities of the project partners.
- Guide the exploration of the policy and regulatory landscape in the context of the project, as well as to encourage active participation in standardization processes for relevant topics and items developed by Smart Droplets.

Phases

A division of the DEC plan into four phases (Figure 7) was crucial, ensuring both its successful implementation and the completion of the aforementioned objectives. The four phases of the DEC plan (Phase 1: Mission, Strategy, Vision, Phase 2: Raise awareness, Phase 3: Synergies and network multipliers, Phase 4: Post-project sustainability & Impact) last from the beginning of the project until after its end, enhancing post-project sustainability.

Figure 7: Smart Droplets DEC phases figure

Phase 1: Mission, Strategy, Vision (M01-M06)

During the first 6 months of the project, we established the foundation for all subsequent communication, dissemination, and exploitation of results. A recognisable project identity has been designed through a strong visual identity (facilitated by a brand book – Annex A) and digital presence (website, social media). This phase will also include creating the first promotional materials (brochure, banner, press release) planning event

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participation, compiling and evaluating potential synergies. Specific activities have been distributed among partners and a preliminary time- schedule has been issued. All partners have been informed about the specific guidelines that they need to follow for D&C outreach and reporting.

Phase 2: Awareness, Consideration & Demonstration (M06-M24)

During the second phase and as the project results unfold, the focus will be to:

- Generate and retain leads by providing up-to-date valuable content.
- Establish ties with other related projects through participatory workshops/events, e- Newsletters, panel discussions, and key umbrella initiatives.

More importantly, during this phase, the ‘explore and transform’ events will be organised, where value chain partners will network and share knowledge. Additional and updated promotional materials such as brochures, videos, rollups, etc. will be developed to disseminate the findings and engage seafood producers, processors, and other relevant enterprises.

Phase 3: Synergies & Network multipliers (M24-48)

During the third phase there will be focus on exploitation and developing a go-to-market strategy for the project’s result such as Smart Droplets solution, Retrofit kit, Sprayer with a direct injection system. A sustainability plan will be created identifying potential private or public funding, to sustain results beyond the end of the project. Post-project dissemination and communication (7 years after the project completion) FSH will maintain key dissemination and communication tools after the completion of the project by:

- Maintaining the project’s website and social media accounts, this will include reposting relevant research or work done by project partners and posting links to events, and open access publications.
- Updating partner contact details on the website each semester to facilitate engagement with key internal and external stakeholders and potential collaborators, incl. the co-programmed partnership on AI, Data and Robotics and funded actions related to this partnership.
- Responding to enquiries from the website.
- Continuing to pursue synergies and cooperation with new projects and initiatives.
- Providing links to these projects and initiatives on the website to direct interested parties to the most relevant and up to date entities continue the work begun by Smart Droplets.

These measures aim both to highlight the ongoing use and reuse of the projects results and ensure lasting interest and engagement with the project’s broader objectives. They will be expanded upon and further developed in the final iteration of the DEC plan. In addition, a multi- faceted, sustainability plan with tools to maintain and strengthen the ecosystem, ongoing collaborations and support the forward trajectory of Smart Droplets solutions will be created as part of the deliverable Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy which was developed on M06 and will be updated annually (M18, M30, M42).

2.4. Target Groups

The Smart Droplets project recognizes that effective engagement spans beyond a mere proclamation of innovation. It necessitates a strategic understanding of diverse stakeholders, each with their distinct interests and aspirations. This cognizance prompted an intricate classification of target groups, an endeavor that began with the project’s inception and has evolved through the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan.

Smart Droplets’ resonance is not limited to a universal message; it’s in the precision with which it caters to the specific objectives of each group. While the overarching ambition is to advance agricultural practices through technology, the project acknowledges that real impact is born from customized communication.

Within this framework, Smart Droplets’ target groups emerge as focal points, each deserving of a tailored approach:

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Smart Droplets has identified **seven (7) key target groups (TGs)** to achieve the D&C objectives:

1. Tech Manufacturers and System Integrators
2. Farmers
3. Agrifood Extension service providers
4. AI/Data/Robotics providers
5. Researchers & Academia
6. EDIH/DIHs/ AI, Data and Robotics Innovation Networks
7. Policy Makers and Regulators

More precisely, distinctive key messages have been crafted for each target group, succinctly encapsulating the singular advantages that Smart Droplets and its outcomes offer, presented in a clear and comprehensible statement (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Smart Droplets target groups and their key messages

TG#1: Tech Manufacturers and System Integrators

Industrial automation equipment, robotics, tractors manufacturers, sprayer manufacturers, hardware, robot system integrators, software and middleware developers

Message for this TG: *Be at the forefront of digital agriculture, enter new markets, expand portfolios and network with end users, researchers and policymakers.*

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TG#2: Farmers

Apple farmers, Wheat farmers; farmers in Spain and Lithuania, European farm managers/administrators/farmers, all types of farmers/farming activities that require/apply fertilization and/or pesticides through spraying

Message for this TG: *Unlock the potential of SFTs and understand what is truly efficient, sustainable & economical at crop management level.*

TG#3: Agrifood Extension service providers

Public & private service providers, and agricultural consultants; other AKIS actors

Message for this TG: *Offer clients the most up-to-date knowledge and tools for selecting, using SFTs for crop management.*

TG#4: AI/Data/Robotics providers

AI Associations, Data/Robotics Associations

Message for this TG: *Support businesses in their digital transformations and promote cooperation between industry and agriculture through AI, data and robotics.*

TG#5: Researchers & Academia

EIP-AGRI & Thematic Networks; EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, SWG SCAR-AKIS, Multi-actor projects & Platforms

Message for this TG: *Contribute to cutting-edge research in digital agriculture and take advantage of interdisciplinary opportunities and collaborations between similar goal-oriented projects.*

TG#6: EDIH/DIHs/ AI, Data and Robotics Innovation Networks

Agrifood, Robotics, AI, Deep-tech DIHs, Machinery DIHs, European Robotics Network, The European Robotics Research Infrastructure Network, ELISE

Message for this TG: *Gain first-hand opportunities to work with and test ground-breaking AI and robotics technologies and bring new opportunities to your DIHs members.*

TG#7: Policy Makers and Regulators

Agricultural & env. authorities; CAP governance bodies (e.g., paying agencies & certification bodies); standardization bodies; EU's DG AGRI, DG ENV, Public Env. monitoring authorities

Message for this TG: *Implement digital agriculture-centred policies based on evidence and farm data and monitor/evaluate the sustainability and impact of those policy measures at the farm, regional, national level.*

Smart Droplets employs a spectrum of communication channels to engage these groups, with specific tools and channels strategically scheduled to reach the identified target groups as depicted below:

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Figure 9: Smart Droplets target groups and corresponding DC activities/channels

Additionally, to approach furthermore the above-mentioned target groups, the project's multi-actor approach will extend to the creation and implementation of the DEC plan, which means:

- Translating materials into partner's languages when applicable and favourable.
- Focusing on communicating information that matters to the information recipient.
- Using language, vocabulary and communication channels that are appealing and audience appropriate.
- Seeking synergies and collaboration opportunities with other projects, initiatives, networks, with and between academia, industry and government.
- Capitalizing on partners existing connections, networks and programs.
- Fostering knowledge exchange activities and discussion.

In weaving these strategies, Smart Droplets strives for comprehensive reach and enduring influence. By recognizing the specific needs of each target group, the project ensures that its groundbreaking innovations foster transformative change in the agricultural landscape, one droplet at a time.

3. Dissemination and Communication Channels, Tools, and Activities

This section outlines the dissemination and communication means that will be used to connect with the Smart Droplets target groups.

3.1. Visual Identity

To target the broadest possible audience, Smart Droplets has created a strong, memorable brand that visually reflects the unique identity and objectives of the project. The visual identity guidelines are in line with the obligations of beneficiaries regarding information and communication and dissemination measures included in Article 17.2 — Visibility — European flag and funding statement and 17.3 Quality of information — Disclaimer of the Grant Agreement Nr.

Smart Droplets will exploit multiple digital platforms to share updates and results and to stimulate ongoing dialogue with stakeholders. Posts and other inputs will be curated to the target audiences at a frequency of once a week, to demonstrate consistency and accessibility.

The project's visual identity includes a logo, as well as relevant templates and guidelines for the partners on the rules of using the communication elements aimed at promoting the Smart Droplets project and properly acknowledging EU funding.

The visual identity is the visible representation of the project. A strong visual identity combines images, colours and shapes to create a powerful, memorable message to the viewer. Smart Droplets' visual identity was created considering the following:

- **Simplicity:** The selected visual identity must be able to tell the story of the project in a simple manner
- **Relevance:** An appropriate aesthetic that can be easily correlated with the project's objectives
- **Uniqueness:** The elements selected must lead to the design of a recognisable and unique visual identity
- **Versatility:** A logo that can be easily used in different communication channels (digital and printed)
- **Memorability:** Colours and design of the logo should make it easy to remember

3.1.1. Logo

The logo will be used in all internal and external communication and dissemination activities (project website, presentations, flyers, press releases, etc.) to help enhance brand continuity and raise awareness. 3 logo variations have been selected for different uses (Annex B). The Smart Droplets logo includes the name of the project as its main concept, with the usage of a clear and modern font, and icons representing digital technologies/innovations, that can be easily correlated with the agricultural sector. The most frequently used logo for the communication and dissemination material is shown in the figure below.

Figure 10: Smart Droplets most used logo

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The colour palette was selected to represent the project's values: agriculture, technology, open communication, and courage. The colours are optimized for use on both screen (RGB) and print (CMYK) and the contrast is optimal for black and white printing.

Figure 11: Smart Droplets colours

To increase project's recognition, extra graphics (covers), that accompany the Smart Droplet's logo on the website and the social media accounts of the project, have been designed (Annex C) to create a maximum recognition value for our target audiences. This coherent visual communication makes Smart Droplets recognisable and easily differentiable in the social media domain.

3.1.2. EU Emblem

All Smart Droplets dissemination and communication material will acknowledge the requirements set out by the European Union and include the EU flag, the source of funding at the Grant agreement number 101070496.

Figure 12: EU recognition visual

The ready-to-use EU emblem including the funding statement can be downloaded in all EU languages.⁴

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en

3.1.3. Disclaimer for publications

In addition to the EU Emblem, all dissemination and communication material must include the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

3.1.4. Templates

Smart Droplets will be presented in numerous events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results.

A **presentation template (ppt)** has been designed in line with the Smart Droplets graphic identity to maintain consistency, and professionalism and promote its recognition. The presentation template can be seen below.

Figure 13: Smart Droplets presentation template

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The Smart Droplets **Deliverable Template (doc)** (Annex D) is also consistent with communication and dissemination material graphic identity and will be used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project's logo in a prominent position, its name, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number, and title), as well as the writer's information.

Figure 14: Smart Droplets deliverable template

An additional **text template (doc)** for written communication includes the logo and the EU emblem to maintain consistency with the project's visual identity.

Figure 15: Smart Droplets Simple template for text documents

3.1.5. Brochure

Brochures will be distributed at the project's events (regional and national workshops) to provide concise project information relevant to the target groups. Three 3-fold brochures have been created in total for this purpose, and each of these are available for distribution during the three different phases of the project. All the brochures have been uploaded in the common drive of the project, in order all the partners to be able to find them and translate them in their languages in case they organise or participate in national events. All 3 brochures can be found in the Annex E.

3.1.6. Posters and Factsheets

For the Smart Droplets project, 3 out of 3 posters have been designed, each one representing a different case study. The 1st poster is showcasing the project's main expected impact and purposes. The 2nd poster is presenting Apple Orchard Pilot Facts, while the 3rd focuses on Wheat Farm Pilot Facts (Annex F). Additionally, a set of three informative factsheets has been developed, providing project at a glance (overall budget, Coordinator, Grant Agreement ID, start and end date of the project), as well as its objectives, challenges and its consortium (Annex G).

3.2. Communication Material

Smart Droplets communication materials have been designed and prepared to deliver and promote the needed public awareness of the project and include both digital and physical forms to increase public perception and the overall domain of the project's influence. Creating both the online and offline (physical material) Smart Droplets ensures that its mission and vision and the related outcomes reach the needed target audience with ease and efficiency. The major advantage of offline communication is the physical, tangible dimension of occupying space to captivate the needed audience during a project's participation in events, conferences, and other manifestations. The project's roll-up banner (Annex H) will be used to promote and present the project at physical meetings and gatherings and a promotional kit has been created including stickers, face masks, folders, and pens that will be distributed to attract a larger audience (Annex I). Posters, brochures and fact sheets are also additional material created for better communication and idea raising on the project for online and offline situations. The previously mentioned communication material has been designed in order to fit with all of Smart Droplets' groups while communicating our objectives and mission in a fun, understandable and engaging way. Materials such as this are focused and geared toward creating initial awareness about the project, its aims, activities, and results. It should be pointed out that, as a best practice, it is beneficial to follow certain rules when utilizing offline material – regardless of the strategies to be implemented, e.g.: well-prepared headlines, wide use of colours, focus on the benefits – and keeping the tone and the message aligned to the intended target audience. To achieve this goal, a brand book has been also developed, to make sure that the produced communication material is in line with the project's visual identity.

3.3. Communication Tools and Channels

3.3.1. Website

The Smart Droplets website (<https://smartdroplets.eu/>) has already been developed and the landing page of the website was released on (M2). The project's website serves the purpose of the primary communication and dissemination platform and enables target groups and Smart Droplets' stakeholders access to the project development and results, and to see and assess the added-value and the impact of digital solutions in agriculture. The site was developed and officially released on M6 with all the partners contributing for its successful updating. The project website hosts all public dissemination deliverables, and promote relevant content (news, editorials, videos, events, etc.) for key stakeholder groups, thus engaging them in the content and objectives of the project. The website also hosts digital visualizations of project processes and results, to make them accessible to a wider audience. The addition of this content relies fully on the progress of the project and will thus be updated and expanded as the project evolves. **In the forthcoming months, we anticipate further enhancements to the website, aimed at integrating additional pertinent project-related information and**

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partner-specific details. Finally, the website is also mobile-friendly, increasing accessibility and maximizing the impact of the project.

Figure 16: Smart Droplets website

The Smart Droplets website has a twofold role:

- it will serve as the principal reference point, explaining the project's aims, providing new updates, and documents for download, and enabling access to social media accounts of the project.
- it will act as a resource center for research on topics related to digital agricultural technologies, providing important updates that have an impact.

Delivered in M3 and within the scope of this deliverable, the Smart Droplets website is hosted at <https://smartdroplets.eu> and contains the following sections and features.

- **Home/Landing page**

Includes the project logo, image, project graphics, social media icons (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare, YouTube, Instagram), a button for sign-up in the Smart Droplets newsletter and a navigation menu providing easy access to information on the project.

Figure 17: Smart Droplets "Landing page"

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- **About us**

This section of the website has quick facts about the project, the expected impact that is to be updated as the project evolves, and objectives.

About Us

Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data, and robotic technologies

Call:
HORIZON-CL4-2021

Duration:
01 September 2022 > 28 February 2026

Project ID:
101070496

OBJECTIVES

Smart Droplets' main objective is to **advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical applications for resource optimisation and minimisation of chemical waste.** It will use existing technologies (>TRL 7) developed within but not limited to

2) Introduce a robotic solution for autonomous spraying. A retrofit (robotic) tractor and an advanced sprayer will be deployed in real farms to address the challenge of resource optimization and waste minimization, targeting chemical and nutrient over-application and

Figure 18: Smart Droplets "About us" tab

- **Our partners**

A list of consortium partners, accompanied by a short description of their role in the project, their expertise is provided in this section of the website.

Smart Droplets

Home About Us Pilots Resources Newsroom Our Partners Contact Us

Logo of a woman's profile

WAGENINGEN
UNIVERSITY & RESEARCH

eureca!

VizLore

FOODSCALE HUB

AGREENCULTURE
Smart tools for smart farming

AgriFood Lithuania

AGROMA
SINCE 1977

FEMAC

Figure 19: Smart Droplets "Our partners" tab

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- **Pilots**

A short description of all the two pilots that will assess SFTs and spraying solutions under real conditions is explained. This part of the website is envisioned as a live and continuously growing section that is to be expanded once the project enters the pilot-driven months.

Figure 20: Smart Droplets “Pilots” tab

- **Resources**

This section of the website will house all ‘ready-to-print material including posters, brochures, project factsheets, notebook, folder, roll-ups, banners, stickers, and a printable brand book and guidelines. Additionally, this segment will house links to public project deliverables deposited on Zenodo as well as the Open Access publications that will be created during the project’s lifespan, ensuring far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports, greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community and improve the likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse project’s results rather than start ab initio, thereby helping in terms of reproductivity and continuity of research results.

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Figure 21: Smart Droplets “Resources” tab

- **Newsroom**

Press releases and posts will be the main content presented here and will inform stakeholders of all project’s activities and upcoming events.

Figure 22: Smart Droplets “Newsroom” tab

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Contact us

All the contact information of the Smart Droplets project will be available under this section enabling the easiest communication with our stakeholders through email (info@smartdroplets.eu).

Smart Droplets

Home About Us Pilots Resources Newsroom Our Partners Contact Us

For more information on Smart Droplets, its results, ongoing and upcoming activities email us or send us a message.

Subject

Name *

Work email *

Message *

Privacy acceptance *

Project Coordination
Dr. Spyros Fountas
Associate Professor

Agricultural University of Athens
75 Iera Odos Str. 11855, Athens, Greece

sfountas@aaua.gr

Project Communication
Grigoris Chatzikostas
VP for Business Development

Foodscale Hub

LEONTOS SOFOU 20, THERMI THESSALONIKIS,
57001, Greece

info@foodscalehub.com

Figure 23: Smart Droplets “Contact us” tab

The **Privacy Policy**, together with the **Terms and Conditions** have also been included in the Smart Droplets website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors’ use of the website.

Smart Droplets

Home About Us Pilots Resources Newsroom Our Partners Contact Us

Privacy policy

This privacy policy governs the use of your personal data by Smart Droplets project – this project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070496; communicate with us via e-mail, telephone, the contact form available on the website and our social media channels; LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, Instagram (hereafter referred to as "Social Media Channels"); or interact with us at fairs and events.

NOTE: If you want information on how we process personal data via cookies on our Website, you are kindly referred to our Cookie Policy.

1. Who is responsible for the processing of your personal data?

1.1 Your personal data are processed by Foodscale Hub, dissemination and communication partner of the Smart Droplets project – this project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070496. You can contact us via e-mail at info@smartdroplets.eu.

1.2 Foodscale Hub reserves the right to modify, change or amend this Privacy Policy at its own discretion and from time to time. Such modifications, changes or amendments shall be communicated via the Website. In case of questions or comments with regard to the modifications, changes or amendments, you can inform us by sending an e-mail to info@smartdroplets.eu.

2. What categories of personal data do we process?

2.1 When you fill out the contact form on our Website, or contact us via e-mail, telephone or Social Media Channels, we collect:

- the basic identity information you provide us with, such as name, e-mail address, postal address, telephone number, the company you work

Figure 24: Smart Droplets “Privacy policy” tab

Figure 25: Smart Droplets "Cookies policy" tab

As mentioned above, partners played a pivotal role in curating the website's content. FSH provided templates that served as a foundation, enabling partners to contribute pertinent information aligned with their expertise. By utilizing these templates, partners efficiently contributed to the site's content, ensuring uniformity and coherence across various sections. The templates that have been provided to the partners, depending on their role in the project, were the following:

Work Package description for the website	
WPx	
WP leader	
Duration	
Short description of the WPx	

Figure 26: Template for WPs description

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Partner description for the website	
Full name of the partner	
Short name of the partner	
Country	
Webpage	
Contact person	
Contact person Title	
Contact's email	
Short description of the partner	
Short description of partner's role in the project	
Link to the logo of the institution in high resolution	

Figure 27: Template for Partners description

During the first reporting period, the Smart Droplets project's website demonstrated remarkable performance and engagement. The captivating and insightful content drew substantial interest, as evidenced by the significant number of clicks and visits. Visitors displayed genuine curiosity in exploring the project's innovative approaches and solutions, underscoring the effectiveness of the presented information. This highlights the relevance of the content and also signifies the growing recognition of Smart Droplets as a leading initiative in the field of precision agriculture. Based on the analytics below, 917 unique users visited our website and explored its content for almost a minute.

Figure 28: Smart Droplets website analytics

3.3.2. Social Media Channels

The project aims to have a strong social media presence and establish two-way communication channels, to better reach out and interact with target audiences and the broader public. To enhance interactive communication, six (6) media channels were selected based on the following three factors:

1. The most **cost-effective** set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholders' groups.
2. The most **adequate, valid, and powerful** media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and number of key-stakeholders, and
3. The most **popular** social media platforms used by Smart Droplets' partners, to communicate and interact with their customers and other stakeholders.

Smart Droplets is registered and active (M3) on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, SlideShare, YouTube and Instagram, and has established metrics for each channel to monitor its effectiveness and implement mitigation measures when necessary.

Figure 29: Smart Droplets Social Media Channels

The social media described above have been selected to further enhance the multi-actor approach of the project. Different kinds of stakeholders require different means of approach. In that sense, the following characteristics have been considered.

- **LinkedIn:** This channel is used mainly for creating awareness and generating networking and collaboration opportunities, due to its professional character and style of communication. Smart Droplets will use this channel to reach all identified target groups, by sharing updates about project key activities.

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- **YouTube:** This channel is mainly used for awareness and training purposes due to its nature and features. Smart Droplets will use this channel to reach any stakeholder interested in data in agriculture, by making available: webinars, testimonial videos on the identified case studies, interviews and outreach videos. Similarly, the content of this social media platform is targeted to all identified target groups of the project.
- **Twitter:** This channel is used mainly for building awareness and enhancing public relations. Twitter is also often used to provide real time updates and quickly spread information regarding all fields of interest. Smart Droplets will use this channel to reach all identified target groups by focusing on workshops and events that will be happening throughout its course.
- **Facebook:** This channel is used mainly for building relationships and maintaining connections with peers and contacts. It is a good platform to build loyalty to the existing network base. Because of the plain language and messages, the content can reach out to several target groups, regardless of social and business backgrounds. Smart Droplets will use this channel to reach all identified target groups.
- **SlideShare:** This channel is mainly used for communication and education purposes. Project presentations will be uploaded for easy access to anyone interested.

To maximise visibility and impact of the project, Smart Droplets exploits the consortium's already developed social media networks (both private and businesses related). In this context consortium members are sharing, comment, publish, and retweet - this depends on the form of social media outlet - content from the Smart Droplets social media accounts and website. Such partner-driven communication efforts also positively result in increased traction for project-related work and as well as increased traffic on partner's websites and social media. Partners are also encouraged to create relevant content to the project's actions and share it through their channels. A template was created to gather all the needed information from each partner such as the links to their official social media accounts.

After selecting the most favourable and appropriate channels for Smart Droplets several parameters listed below should be considered and used as guidelines when creating social media content and they go as follows:

- I. **Interactivity** is the main pillar of the generated content and is the best way to reach and engage an audience. Posts will be easily understood by different target groups, including non-specialists, creating traction and engagement.
- II. **Eye catching posts** will lead to higher conversions. By prioritising the creation of visuals and graphics with informative content, Smart Droplets will gain a unique dimension online and will overall lead to higher post engagement.
- III. **Adaptability** is important as users can access online content from various devices. Thus, the adaptability of social media assets to the format and functioning of several devices is necessary to ensure the maximization of asset placement, especially considering the use of mobile phones.

3.3.2.1. Social Media DOs & DON'Ts

A set of recommendations for effective social media engagement has been created to support SmartDroplets partners. This will facilitate the processes followed by partners regarding social media communication, and will boost the project's performance in its social media channels. Figure 30 provides a concise list of DOs and DON'Ts.

Figure 30: Social Media Recommended actions

Social Media Strategy and Key Points

Social media posts are published on project's social media accounts on LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter and Instagram, with a standard frequency of one post per week, and adjusted according to the project's needs. This social media strategy aims to maintain the audience's engagement and inform about various topics related to the project, which are presented below:

- Updates regarding Smart Droplets partners event participation and activities including conferences, webinars, workshops ect.
- Smart Droplets Case Studies
- Smart Droplets internal meetings insights and important updates
- Interesting reads, articles or news related to the project's main concepts, namely data spaces, food systems and data economy.
- Smart Droplets featured in media outlets
- Newsletter & blog posts updates
- Relevant International Days

All followers/ subscribers of the Smart Droplets social media channels are given the opportunity to react in posts, comment and spark conversations or repost the project's content, depending on the respective social media platform.

Additionally, to effectively share information on social media our consortium will design posts based on how the audience consumes the message, considering user responses and engagements. The following figure explains the steps that a visually appropriate social media post shall contain and based on these high-efficiency posts will be created during project's lifespan:

Figure 31: Assessment and criteria used for Smart Droplets Social Media posts

3.3.2.2. Hashtags

Another important tool for enhanced social media presence is the use of hashtags. Creating hashtags that are relevant helps users stay in touch with the project and its outcomes while also making it easy to find Smart Droplets-generated knowledge. Hashtags convey the main topics of Smart Droplets into easily digestible and engaging keyword phrases and that help increase visibility in the social media environment while making key messages stand out and influence the relevant communities. Hashtags also have internal benefits to the consortium, as they will help track and analyse quantitative and qualitative data generated on the above-mentioned social media platforms. For the generation of hashtags, feedback will be asked and received by all project partners, to safeguard that the bulk of concepts, ideas, tools/services are captured and incorporated. The project will have official distinctive hashtags seen in the Figure below, which are used to monitor the posts related to the project. The preliminary consortium hashtags in Smart Droplets communication are as follows:

Figure 32: Smart Droplets Hashtag cloud

In addition, the hashtags #HorizonEurope, #ResearchImpactEU, suggested by the European Commission, accompany each post to emphasise the EU direction of the project.

3.3.2.3. LinkedIn

A LinkedIn profile (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/smart-droplets/>) was created, aiming to facilitate networking with the Smart Droplets target audiences and promoting the project's activities, updates and interesting news. As such, all the project's news are published on its LinkedIn profile, and partners will have the

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opportunity to start conversations on particular topics, to attract wider audiences. Figure 33 provides an overview of the Smart Droplets LinkedIn profile.

Figure 33: Smart Droplets LinkedIn Profile

LinkedIn analytics helps us evaluate the success of our professional networking and information dissemination efforts. Figure 34 provides an overview of the amount of followers gained over the course of the year, with the biggest growth happening from April 2023 and onwards.

Figure 34: Smart Droplets LinkedIn Metrics: Followers

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Smart Droplets LinkedIn page is recording exceptional engagement rates, with the lowest being 4.4% and the highest 15.3%, which is a clear indication of the compelling nature of our content and the high degree of audience interaction. This figure underscores the resonance of our initiatives with the professional community on LinkedIn. Given the platform's user base of professionals, academics and industry leaders, this engagement is significant.

Figure 35: Smart Droplets LinkedIn Metrics: Engagement Rate

3.3.2.4. Facebook

Smart Droplets' Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/SmartDroplets>) was created to communicate directly with target audiences on an individual level. Facebook is used to raise awareness for the Smart Droplets project and results targeting the general public and farmers who are mainly using the particular social media channel. Figure 36 provides an overview of Smart Droplet's Facebook profile.

Figure 36: Smart Droplets Facebook page

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Reviewing Facebook analytics provides essential insights into the reach and effectiveness of our project. These metrics show how our posts are interacting with the public and farmers, demonstrating the level of awareness we've created. Below is an overview of the page's metrics for the month of July 2023.

Figure 37: Smart Droplets Facebook Metrics Overview

3.3.2.5. Instagram

Smart Droplets' Instagram account (<https://www.instagram.com/smartdroplets/>), will be used for communicating with members of the public. To effectively utilize this social media platform for communicating the scope and objectives of the project, Smart Droplets will post pictures and videos from the meetings and summarised events including that of the two pilot cases once the timeline fits.

Figure 38: Smart Droplets Instagram Account

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3.3.2.6. Twitter

A Twitter account was created (<https://twitter.com/SmartDroplets>) to increase the visibility of the project and engage specific audiences such as policy makers and advisors. Smart Droplets will use short messages (less than 280 characters) to interact with them, and post news, events, and updates on the project's status.

Twitter's popularity and concise, simple format makes it extremely important and useful for informing and engaging with our targeted audiences and their respective communities. Twitter will also be used to connect to 'high influencers' in the research and business topics of the Smart Droplets project to successfully build an active community.

Figure 39: Smart Droplets Twitter Account

Analysing Twitter metrics provides a summary of our real-time engagement and reach. These figures show how well information was disseminated and how engaging our content was. Boasting an engagement rate of 11% on the Smart Droplets Twitter page signifies a high level of active involvement and interest from our audience, well above industry averages. This figure demonstrates the effectiveness of our content strategy in fostering dialogue and attracting attention to our renewable energy initiatives, underlining the resonance of our project within the Twitter community.

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Your Tweets earned **765 impressions** over this **91 day** period

Figure 40: Smart Droplets Twitter Metrics Overview

3.3.2.7. SlideShare

A SlideShare account (<https://www.slideshare.net/SmartDroplets>) has been created and the material that is projected to be uploaded are visual formats that will help to resonate more with our readers, reach an audience that is interested in our content and cultivate more opportunities for future collaborations.

Figure 41: Smart Droplets SlideShare Page

3.3.2.8. YouTube

A YouTube account (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4e1fcol5HBhXLvMfAWdva>) for the Smart Droplets project will be used in order to host and promote the project's videos, which will be of wide variety, such as interviews, promotional videos, insights from the real-life demonstrations.

Figure 42: Smart Droplets YouTube

3.3.3. Newsletter

An electronic newsletter is published on a quarterly basis, once every three months to provide updates and relevant information to subscribers and consortium members. This includes the latest developments, partners features, test case results and activities as well as upcoming events, workshops, demonstrations and where to find recent reports and publications.

Subscriptions can take place on the Smart Droplets website. It should be highlighted that Smart Droplets, pays special attention to security and respect of the privacy and confidentiality of the user's personal data and newsletter recipients are asked to provide their consent prior to sending any information related to the project. All relevant activities and aspects related to personal data will be fully compliant with the applicable national, European, and international legal framework, and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation 2016/6798. Interested parties are able to subscribe and unsubscribe at any given point from the Smart Droplets Newsletters and all the collected data are stored and saved in the responsible partner's servers. These data are not be accessible from other third parties. To achieve a broader distribution and facilitate the engagement of as many stakeholders as possible, Smart Droplets partners are encouraged to promote the newsletters to their contacts who may be interested in the project.

The image shows a subscription form with a light green background. At the top, it says "Subscribe to get all information, latest news & other insights about Smart Droplets". Below this is a white input field with the placeholder text "Your email address". At the bottom of the form is a blue button with the text "Get started".

The footer contains three columns of information. The first column is titled "Project Coordination" and lists Dr. Spyros Fountas, Associate Professor at the Agricultural University of Athens. The second column is titled "Project Communication" and lists Grigoris Chatzikostas, VP for Business Development at Foodscale Hub. The third column features the European Union logo and text stating "Co-funded by the European Union" and "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme".

Figure 43: Smart Droplets Subscription form

In total, 3 newsletters have been published during the project's lifetime, with the fourth one to getting published in the upcoming weeks, completing successfully the Communication KPI, C2.6 – Newsletter for the 1st reporting period, where the goal was 4 newsletters. The content that is uploaded is informative, providing knowledge around relevant to the project topics as well as the latest updates of Smart Droplets. The high quality of content resulted in the completion of another KPI goal, and this time of C2.5 - No. of newsletter subscribers. More specifically the target for this period was 100 and we achieved more than 101 subscribers.

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Smart Droplets

Your audience has **101** contacts. **101** of these are subscribers.

Overview Manage contacts ▾ Add contacts ▾ Subscriber preferences Settings ▾ 🔍

Overview

101 Subscribed Contacts	0 Non-subscribed Contacts	0 Unsubscribed Contacts	9 Cleaned Contacts
----------------------------	------------------------------	----------------------------	-----------------------

Audience performance

Figure 44: Smart Droplets subscribers

Newsletter [Issue 01](#)

Issue 01 of the newsletter was released on 30/12/2022 and was focused on introducing the project and presenting the main actions taken by the project partners in the first 3 months since its kick off meeting. The topics it included were:

- Smart Droplets Introduction
- Smart Droplets Kick-Off Meeting
- 1st Press Release
- Participation in *Paving the way towards the next generation of R&I Excellence in AI, Data and Robotics*
- Introduction of Consortium Partners

Figure 45: Smart Droplets 1st Newsletter

Figures 46 and 47 present an overview of the first newsletter analytics, regarding the audience's location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens, and total clicks.

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Successful deliveries	47	92.2%	Clicks per unique opens	0%
Total opens	35		Total clicks	0

Figure 46: Newsletter Issue 01 Analytics

Top locations by opens

Figure 47: Newsletter Issue 01 audience's location

Newsletter [Issue 02](#)

Smart Droplets

Welcome!
We're thrilled to bring you the latest advancements in agricultural technologies that can lead to more effective and efficient practices in pesticide and fertilizer usage. Let's explore how using data, digital twins and AI, and enhancing digital skills can promote sustainable spraying practices!

Data-driven agriculture
Discover the future of farming with data-driven agriculture! Unveiling the potential of cutting-edge technologies, see shed light on how data-driven agriculture can revolutionize the way we grow crops, manage resources, and optimize farming practices. Learn how Smart Droplets' innovative solutions can lead to higher crop yields, reduced environmental impact, and improved decision making for farmers, all while ensuring a sustainable future for our planet.

What are Digital Twins?
Gain valuable insight into this groundbreaking technology! With virtual replicas of real-world plants and crops, farmers are now able to simulate, analyze and optimize their operations when it comes to crop care and management. This facilitates data-driven decision-making, improving resource management, preventing pests & diseases and enhancing crop yields. Discover how Smart Droplets is at the forefront of implementing these innovations to transform the industry.

How can AI change spraying?
Discover how AI-powered spraying technology is transforming the industry by enhancing precision, efficiency, and sustainability. Learn how Smart Droplets' innovative solutions leverage machine learning algorithms to analyze real-time data and make

Digital skills: Are they needed in agriculture?
The short answer is yes! Digital skills can optimize agricultural practices and drive the industry forward. Among others, data analysis, remote sensing and precision agriculture can empower farmers and enhance their productivity, while promoting sustainability. Smart Droplets aims to contribute to this with the **Smart Droplets Academy**, a yearly 10-hour training program aimed at strengthening the capacity of non-experts on the topics of AI, AI ethics, Data and Robotics.

See more

Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter

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Figure 48: Newsletter Issue 02 Overview

The 2nd issue, released on 28/04/2023m was focused on informing the public, including non-specialists, regarding the role of data and AI in agriculture, through blog posts published on the Smart Droplets website. More specifically, the topics included:

- Data-driven agriculture.
- Introduction to Digital Twins.
- “How can AI change spraying?”
- Digital skills and why they are necessary in agriculture.

In the figures 49 and 50, there is an overview of the 2nd newsletter analytics, regarding the audience's location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens, and total clicks.

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48 Opened	6 Clicked	7 Bounced	0 Unsubscribed
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Successful deliveries 95 93.1% Clicks per unique opens 12.5%
 Total opens 80 Total clicks 6

Figure 49: Newsletter Issue 02 Analytics

Top locations by opens

USA	47	82.5%
Greece	9	15.8%
Belgium	1	1.8%

Figure 50: Newsletter Issue 02 audience's location

Newsletter Issue 03

How can autonomous tractors benefit farmers and SMEs?

From wooden plows, steam and diesel engines, to autonomous tractors that use various technologies such as GPS and AI, tractors have come a long way. According to Marder Intelligence, the expected CAGR of autonomous tractors from 2023 to 2028 will grow by 26.1%. The main factors for this increase include the growing demand for food, the need for efficient farming as well as the reduction in arable land.

Agricultural sprayers: from handheld to high-tech

Historically, agricultural sprayers were simple, handheld devices used for applying pesticides and fertilizers manually. As with the autonomous tractors, the tools used for spraying became motorized, incorporating atomization techniques and GPS to enhance precision. Despite these advancements, there are still issues to be tackled.

Benefits of Direct Injection Spraying (DIS)

In traditional sprayers, water and chemicals are pre-mixed. The disadvantages of this technique include wastage of pesticides and fertilizers, risk of chemical residues in the tank as well as difficulty of adjusting the mix on-the-go. With DIS, farmers have greater flexibility while staying safe and reducing chemical waste, thus contributing to environmental sustainability.

[Learn About Next-Gen Sprayers](#)

Smart Droplets at agROBOfood Network Event!

May 11, 12, 2023, we had the honor of participating in the captivating session on **apping Innovations Across the EU!** at the Agricultural University of Athens, detailed by Mladen Radacic, CEO of FoodScale Hub.

coordinators and WP leaders from Robs4Crops, CoRoSect, SoftGrip, and FlavioDroplets came together to present their groundbreaking initiatives and tackle the challenges of community engagement and implementation in rural robotics.

Smart Droplets on "Exypni Oikonomia" show

Our partner, FoodScale Hub, presented Smart Droplets in the "Exypni Oikonomia" show by TV100 in Thessaloniki, Greece. FoodScale Hub partners explained how Smart Droplets aims to contribute to a more sustainable future in farming, with the reduction of chemicals use, by combining data and technology.

Figure 51: Newsletter Issue 03 Overview

The 3rd Issue, released on 27/06/2023, was focused on educational content regarding the usage of autonomous tractor and agricultural sprayers, as well as Direct Injection Spraying. Additionally, a special section was devoted to the events & TV Shows the Smart Droplets project was presented at. In detail, the updated included were:

- "How can autonomous tractors benefit farmers and SMEs?"
- "Agricultural sprayers: from handheld to high-tech"
- "Benefits of Direct Injection Spraying (DIS)"
- Smart Droplets presentation at AgROBOfood Network Event
- Smart Droplets on "Exypni Oikonomia" TV show

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In the following figure, an overview of the 3rd issue analytics is provided, regarding the audience's location, successful deliveries, clicks per unique opens, total opens, and total clicks.

Figure 52: Newsletter Issue 03 Analytics

Top locations by opens

Figure 53: Newsletter Issue 03 audience's location

3.3.4. Press Outreach

Press releases will be produced and distributed for publication among national/regional/EU press to further promote the project, its latest activities, and developments to a broader audience as well as address more specific stakeholders. The press release will be available on the Smart Droplets website under the tab News Room, and all related publications will be shared on social media channels to disseminate the information. Thus, a press release template has been developed (Annex K) during M3. To maximize our influence on local stakeholders, the consortium is advised to translate all press releases into all 6 of the consortium partners' languages. More specifically:

Number of partners covered by language	Language
3	Greek
1	Dutch
2	Spanish
2	Serbia
1	French
1	Lithuanian

Table 2: Number of different languages Smart Droplets press releases can be translated into

3.3.5. Publications

To have a fully developed communication and dissemination portfolio, Smart Droplets takes into account the much-needed impact to be generated in the scientific domain, and more importantly will integrate itself into the development of several scientific, industry and policy publications as well as practice abstracts. Such publication will target the more technical experts of the targeted stakeholder groups and thus promote the projects and its findings among them. The consortium will put an effort for the majority of publications to implement Open Access and open peer review, in accordance with current EU regulations on Open Access and Open Science. Thus, publications will be potentially published in Open Research Europe and/or open-access journals (green or gold). A key aspect for Open Science is to make collected data available for future research and analysis, while avoiding the exposure of any personal data without consent. The availability of project outputs as Open Access will ensure:

1. far higher citation counts for academic publications and reports.
2. greater impact due to increased visibility with practitioners and the wider stakeholder community (in this project above all farmers and advisors).
3. improve the likelihood that future research and analysis will be able to build on and reuse our results rather than start ab initio, thereby helping in terms of the reproducibility and continuity of research results.

3.3.5.1. Scientific publications

Smart Droplets will strive to publish at least 5 peer-reviewed papers & conference contributions in respected and highly rated journals and scientific magazines. Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project’s results to the research community and providing scientific credibility for the project’s work. This task will be undertaken mostly by the university and research partners and publications will cover several fields of the work performed within the Smart Droplets project, including but not limited to the results of the two pilots, the testing and success of the developed technologies.

During the reporting period, our partner, WUR, has demonstrated noteworthy contributions. At the AgMIP9 event held at Columbia University in New York, NY, USA, on June 26, 2023, WUR presented a poster titled "Optimizing Nitrogen Management in Winter Wheat: A Reinforcement Learning Approach with Crop Growth Models." This insightful contribution highlights our dedication to refining nitrogen management practices through innovative reinforcement learning methods.

Figure 54: Poster titled "Optimizing Nitrogen Management in Winter Wheat: A Reinforcement Learning Approach with Crop Growth Models."

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Moreover, another impactful poster presentation titled "Integrating Process-Based Models and Machine Learning for Crop Yield Prediction" was showcased at the International Conference on Machine Learning held in New York on July 23. These presentations signify our ongoing commitment to advancing the field of precision agriculture and sharing our discoveries with the broader scientific community.

Figure 55: Poster titled "Integrating Process-Based Models and Machine Learning for Crop Yield Prediction."

3.3.5.2. Industry publications

Besides the creation of Press Releases and scientific publications, Smart Droplets aims to publish **30** articles in agriculture and related impactful industry magazines, to make the project and its results are known to the industrial stakeholders. To maximize impact, guidelines and timing for identifying, selecting and producing publications using have been defined:

Figure 56: Smart Droplets article submission process

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3.3.5.3. Recommendations & statements

The uptake of agricultural innovations is in need for the bottom-up approaches of feedback and recommendation integration in order to design the needed policy measures. In that sense Smart Droplets will produce **2** sets of standardization recommendations from findings developed and tested during the project in order to enable an understating and positive impact of deep tech in agricultural environments while targeting policy personnel and experts. Furthermore, during the project Smart Droplets consortium will create **5** joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & networks to further influence decision-making and development in agricultural value chains.

3.3.5.4. Technical Briefs

Smart Droplets will produce **5** tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications. The goal is to develop short summaries that describe the main information/recommendation/practice regarding the deployment of deep-tech in agriculture that can be used by the end-users in order to enhance the sustainability performance and competitiveness of the agricultural sector.

3.3.6. Event Planning

For the Smart Droplets projects, the necessary event planning will take part in two phases. The initial phase is the logging and documentation phase. Twice a year, that is on a 6-month period, an event planning form will be sent to the consortium partners to report on the events that are already in their calendars. Partners are expected to provide the following information: a brief description including the date, location, target groups and a preliminary suggestion as to the role/implication for Smart Droplets (i.e., workshop, booth). Gathering information on relevant events will support decision making of event planning. Nevertheless, the form will be sent to partners, and the responses will be compiled using an online reporting tool for easy reference and record-keeping. Several potential events have already been identified.

For a clearer visualization of schedules and details and promotion of effective coordination of activities, a revised planning table has been created. This enhancement streamlines event management, ensuring each event is planned and executed to maximise its impact and reach.

Smart Droplets Event Planning						
#	Name & Type of event	Event link (if applicable)	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential Smart Droplets involvement

Table 3: Smart Droplets Event Planning Example

Several potential events have already been identified as presented in the following table.

#	Partner	Event	Date	Location	Target Groups	Potential involvement
1	AUA, FSH	Synergy Days	4-5/10/2023	Thessaloniki, Greece	Digital innovators/experts of the agri-food sector/students/	Booth
2	EUT	AGORA TECNOLÓGICA	28/9/2023	Lleida, Catalonia, Spain	Farmers and AgriCooperative,	Talk, presenter

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		FIRA DE SAN MIQUEL			Private sector, government	
3	EUT	ROSCon 2023	29/9/2023	Madrid, Spain	Academia, programmers, students	Talk, presenter (Autonomous robots in AGRICULTURE: localization and navigation strategies using ROS for different agricultural use-cases)
4	EUT	ROBOT 2023	22/11/2023	Coimbra, Portugal	Academia	Talk, presenter
5	FEMAC	FRUIT ATTRACTION 2023	3-5/10/2023	Madrid, Spain	International Growers	Roll-Up
6	AGROMA	AGRITECHNICA 2023	12-18/11/2023	Hanover, Germany	Farmers, Industry stakeholders	
7	FSH	Agrotica (Exhibition)	Annual	Thessaloniki, Greece	Private sector, agri-rural communities	Roll-up, Booth
8	FSH	Panhellenic Congress on the Development of Greek Agriculture (Congress)	Annual	Thessaloniki, Greece	Authorities & Policy Makers	Presentation, Banner
9	FSH	AgriBusiness Forum	Annual	Greece	Industry Associations & Groups, Institutional & Private Partners	Presentation, Banner

Table 4: Potential events for participation

The second phase involves the selection of events as seen in the Figure below. This will be done based on the guidelines shown below. When selecting the events for Smart Droplets to participate in the alignment with the project's objectives and budget should be taken into consideration as well as the need to adapt to the individual activities of each partner.

Guidelines for event selection

Figure 57: Guidelines for event selection

3.3.7. Networking and Synergies

Building synergies and expanding the Smart Droplets ecosystem is a significant priority of the DEC plan. Much of the project’s work will build upon the experience, knowledge and/or data developed by partners during other projects. This collaborative approach will be extended to the DEC and will involve a four-step process.

Figure 58: Networking and Synergies Phases

Phase 1: Identification

Potentially mutually beneficial partnerships and synergies will first be identified. A new template has been created for partners to complete, requesting information on any other project’s networks or initiatives they are currently participating in that could be relevant to Smart Droplets. This catalogues essential details, which can be seen in the following table.

Smart Droplets Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of Initiative(s)	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities

Table 5: Smart Droplets synergies & liaison mapping template

This template is distributed every 6 months to account for new projects that are beginning. Smart Droplets considers both projects that are near completion and those that will run in parallel. Connecting with projects that will be ending, provides network expansion opportunities for Smart Droplets while enabling the other projects to meet sustainability goals and keep the momentum of their project going. Projects, networks, and initiatives running in parallel provide several opportunities to strengthen communication pathways and conduct joint activities. The template (Table 5) has been sent to partners requesting information on any other project’s/networks or initiatives they are relevant to the Smart Droplets project or that they are participating in. This template is included with the planning form so that it is always accessible. FSH consolidates this list every 6 months which is presented below:

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Relevant projects for Smart Droplets	
	<p>OPTIMA will develop an environmentally friendly IPM framework for vineyards, apple orchards and carrots by providing a holistic integrated approach which includes all critical aspects related to integrated disease management, such as i) novel bio-PPPs use, ii) disease prediction models, iii) spectral early disease detection systems and iv) precision spraying techniques. It will contribute significantly to the reduction of the European agriculture reliance on chemical PPPs resulting in reduced use of agrochemicals, lower residues and reduced impacts on human health. OPTIMA will optimize disease prediction models for downy mildew in vineyards, apple scab in apple orchards and alternaria leaf blight in carrots to envisage faster the possibility of disease outspread and developing advanced early detection methods based on spectral imaging and deep learning techniques to precisely localise and quantify the infection. It will evaluate and screen biological and synthetic PPPs for their combined ability to control the selected diseases and weigh the optimum dosage and application timing and identifying and characterize induced host resistance mechanisms to achieve higher and durable resistance. It will enhance and develop three innovative prototype sprayers (for carrots, apple orchards and vineyards) actuating different nozzle types and adopting variable rate control based on canopy characteristics, the pathogen dispersal and disease development. The holistic developed IPM system will be tested and assessed in field conditions with the three selected crops. The advanced sprayer prototypes and the monitoring system will be tested in real-time to record field efficacy and potential discrepancies from the expected effectiveness. OPTIMA will finally, assess health, environmental and socioeconomic impacts of the proposed IPM system in comparison to conventional systems using an extended Life-Cycle approach integrated with Human and Environmental Risk Assessment.</p> <p>http://optima-h2020.eu/the-project/</p>
	<p>Agriculture is susceptible to the cost and scarcity of labour, and making cultivation practices more efficient and sustainable is critical. EU-funded ROBS4CROPS is a vital catalyst in accelerating high-tech robotics and automated technologies in the European food and farm industry. Building upon the existing agricultural machinery, standards, and best practices, the 4-year project will shape and deliver a flexible and modular, fully autonomous system ready for large-scale commercial trials. The trials will be conducted in partnership with commercial farms and business leaders from France, Greece, Spain, and the Netherlands. ROBS4CROPS will significantly reduce farmers' dependency on hired labour, increase safety, reduce the use of inputs and the overall carbon footprint of food production.</p> <p>https://robs4crops.eu/</p>

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	<p>Europe’s agri-food sector is facing a big challenge: ensuring environmentally-friendly production at lower costs and with a shortage of labourers. The solution requires high-tech modernisation of farming. Robotics can play a big role. The agROBOfood project, a consortium of 39 partners aims to accelerate the sector’s digital transformation through the adoption of robotic technologies. To boost the uptake of robotic solutions, it will establish a sustainable network of digital innovation hubs (DIHs). At the heart of the project are innovation experiments (IEs) that will be organised and monitored by the DIHs. The European robotics community will be involved throughout the project to ensure maximum synergy. This will maximise the return of investments from the digital transformation of agri-food.</p> <p>https://agrobofood.eu/</p>
	<p>With robotics technologies advancing at breakneck speeds, many industry sectors are eager to welcome them. One of these is agriculture, which is facing the issue of phytopharmaceutical spraying and a need to reduce their over dosage while retaining efficiency and crop yield. The EU-funded SCORPION project will address many of the challenges involved while also developing a modular unmanned tractor in cooperation with several agricultural and robotics associations, institutions and companies. The goal is to reduce phytopharmaceutical usage while maintaining crop yield, efficiency and value. This machine will initially focus on steep-slope vineyards that present more difficulties during spraying.</p> <p>https://scorpion-h2020.eu/</p>
	<p>The main objective of the project is to design and implement a parameterized, knowledge-based, multi-target food sensitive mini-portable system, with heterogeneous micro-scale photonics for on-the-spot food quality sensing and shelf-life prediction. In particular, the miniaturized smart integrated system will be able to detect food hazards, spoilage (incl. early sign of spoilage) and food fraud through the combined bio-chemical data analysis and additionally will be able to perform food components/additives analysis, food identification and prediction of food shelf-life. The following use case will be addressed during the project: Use case 1: Detection of mycotoxins in various grains and nuts. Aflatoxins detection. A simple, convenient ultraviolet test makes it possible to detect the possible presence of aflatoxin. Use case 2: Detection of early sign of spoilage and spoilage in fruits, vegetables, meat, fish: combined with estimation on product expiration date. Use case 3: Detection of food fraud: Adulteration of alcoholic beverages, oil, milk and meat. 3 sensor devices will be integrated in the miniaturised smart sensor node: i) a MEMS-based near IR spectrometer (950-1900 nm), ii) a UV-VIS spectrometer (450-900 nm) and iii) a micro-camera. Moreover 3 light sources will also be integrated to support the sensing functionality: i) UV-LED, ii) white LED and iii) a miniaturised IR emitter. Smart signal processing of the</p>

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	<p>spectrum images will be performed by an advanced microcontroller, integrated in the sensing device. The data will be communicated to a smartphone device, where the spectroscopy analysis will take place with the help of a cloud-base application connected to a reference database. Advanced detection algorithms will be deployed both in the level of cloud and the smartphone application. PhasmaFOOD system will enable common consumers for on-the-spot food quality sensing and shelf-life prediction.</p> <p>https://phasmafood.eu/</p>
	<p>The IoF2020 project is dedicated to accelerate adoption of IoT for securing sufficient, safe and healthy food and to strengthen competitiveness of farming and food chains in Europe. It will consolidate Europe's leading position in the global IoT industry by fostering a symbiotic ecosystem of farmers, food industry, technology providers and research institutes. The IoF2020 consortium of 73 partners, led by Wageningen UR and other core partners of previous key projects such as FIWARE and IoT-A, will leverage the ecosystem and architecture that was established in those projects. The heart of the project is formed by 19 use cases grouped in 5 trials with end users from the Arable, Dairy, Fruits, Vegetables and Meat verticals and IoT integrators that will demonstrate the business case of innovative IoT solutions for a large number of application areas. A lean multi-actor approach focusing on user acceptability, stakeholder engagement and sustainable business models will boost technology and market readiness levels and bring end user adoption to the next stage. This development will be enhanced by an open IoT architecture and infrastructure of reusable components based on existing standards and a security and privacy framework. Anticipating vast technological developments and emerging challenges for farming and food, the 4-year project stays agile through dynamic budgeting and adaptive decision-making by an implementation board of representatives from key user organizations. A 6 M€ mid-term open call will allow for testing intermediate results and extending the project with technical solutions and test sites. A coherent dissemination strategy for use case products and project learnings supported by leading user organizations will ensure a high market visibility and an increased learning curve. Thus IoF2020 will pave the way for data-driven farming, autonomous operations, virtual food chains and personalized nutrition for European citizens.</p> <p>https://www.iof2020.eu/</p>
<p>EUHUBS4DATA</p>	<p>Most of Europe's SMEs lag behind in data-driven innovation. To tackle this problem, the EU-funded EUHubs4Data project will build a European federation of Data Innovation Hubs based on existing key players in this area and connecting with data incubators and platforms, SME networks, AI communities, skills and training organisations and open data repositories. A European catalogue of data sources and federated data-driven services and solutions will be</p>

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	<p>made accessible to European SMEs, start-ups and web entrepreneurs through the Data Innovation Hubs. Cross-border and cross-sector data-driven experimentation will be facilitated through data-sharing, as well as data- and service interoperability, becoming a reference instrument for growth in a global data economy and contributing to the creation of common European data spaces.</p> <p>https://euhubs4data.eu/</p>
<p>The logo for QuantiFarm features the word "Quanti" in blue with a circuit-like graphic to its left, and "Farm" in green with a leaf-like graphic to its right.</p>	<p>Digital technologies in agriculture (DATs) can grow the sector by enhancing sustainability, performance and competitiveness byte by byte, but only if they are designed to support sustainability. In this context, the EU-funded QuantiFarm project will introduce a comprehensive assessment framework for independent qualitative and quantitative assessment of the multiple costs and benefits of DATs, as well as of their sustainability impact. Following a multi-actor approach, QuantiFarm will carry out 30 test cases across 20 European countries. The test cases will all be in commercial farms of different types, sizes, ownership and operating conditions from seven agricultural sectors. The aim is to assess the DATs used in the farms and feed the results to the QuantiFarm Toolkit to increase awareness and support future decision-making.</p> <p>https://quantifarm.eu/</p>
<p>The logo for CoRoSect features a stylized insect-like graphic in blue and purple above the text "CoRoSect" in a bold, blue, sans-serif font.</p>	<p>Food insecurity represents one of the biggest challenges in the 21st century. Edible insects emerge as a potentially sustainable solution for food for humans and animals. To improve mass production and breeding and reduce their costs, the development of research, innovation, farming protocols and standardisation is necessary as well as the robotisation and automation of insect farms. The EU-funded CoRoSect project focuses on the connection of research on bionomics and the life cycle of insects with new robotics tools and protocols for the automatization of insect farming. The project will establish innovative integrated cognitive robotics ecosystems that will replace operations demanding manual labour or continuous human supervision during the insects' life cycle.</p> <p>https://corosect.eu/</p>
<p>The logo for FlexiRobots features a circular icon with a drone and a robot on a green field, followed by the text "FLEXIGROBOTS" in a bold, blue, sans-serif font.</p>	<p>In an effort to enhance agricultural production, agricultural robots are being increasingly adopted. The number of discreet tasks to be automated, however, significantly reduces the flexibility of current solutions, thus impacting efficiency and limiting their take-up. The EU-funded FLEXIGROBOTS project aims to develop a platform that will help build heterogeneous multi-robot systems, allowing for vastly improved flexibility by using existing robots for multiple tasks. This could help produce higher-value data from a variety of sources and sensors, increasing operational autonomy and precision while greatly reducing costs and encouraging investment in robotics.</p>

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	https://flexigrobots-h2020.eu/
	<p>Labour costs often represent up to 50 % of total production costs in the fresh food industry. Although the sector demands solutions to reduce them, the shift towards robotic automation is obstructed by the complex and contact-rich interactions needed. The EU-funded SoftGrip project will introduce a self-actuating soft gripper for the autonomous picking of delicate white button mushrooms. The project aims for low-cost, intelligent soft robotic grippers with embedded actuation, tactile sensing, recyclable materials and advanced fabrication techniques. It will develop a set of fast-computed modelling algorithms to enhance real-time model-based control schemes and advanced learning capabilities. SoftGrip will develop a learning-by-demonstration framework that will allow the robot to capture human picking skills, extendable to other similar tasks.</p> <p>https://www.softgrip-project.eu/</p>
	<p>Fruit cracking is one of the main physiological disorders limiting fruit quality and yield. It is a peel disorder occurring mainly during the pre-harvest stage due to climatic and environmental conditions and poor orchard management. The EU-funded CrackSense project will develop and upscale sensing technologies providing real-time sensor data through piloting activities concerning the fruit cracking problem in citrus, pomegranate, table grapes and sweet cherries. The Integrated CrackSense Solution will improve the sensor data collected into EU-wide data sets, including Earth Observation Data and other data sets concerning environmental conditions and used to monitor agricultural production. The solution will mitigate the effects of the cracking phenomenon reducing by half the yield losses due to cracking, allowing farmers efficient management and sustainable actions.</p>

Table 6: Relevant projects for Smart Droplets

Phase 2: Evaluation

To ensure synergies will benefit the project and align with Smart Droplets objectives, each potential project, initiatives and network is assessed against qualitative/quantitative indicators such as:

- Relevance.
- Estimated impact (e.g., visibility, added value).
- Feasibility (e.g., timeline and resources).
- Terms for collaboration, etc.

The results of the evaluation are consolidated with the information provided by partners and a final decision will be made by the consortium.

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Phase 3: Contact

Once it has been agreed upon that a synergy should be established, the most appropriate approach for making contact will be decided on a case-by-case basis.

Phase 4: Action

Communication pathways and joint activities will be decided after discussions with their representatives and the Smart Droplets consortium and will include (but are not limited to):

- Joint communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.
- Joint policy events.
- Coordinating research and/or joint publications.
- Sharing data, inputs and/or outputs.
- Participation in the other's events.
- Links to project and project events on website, social media.

Building Collaborative Bridges: Smart Droplets' Synergies

In the realm of agricultural innovation, collaboration is a strategic imperative. The success of projects often hinges on their ability to connect, share insights, and leverage the collective expertise of their peers. Recognizing this, Smart Droplets places a significant emphasis on building robust connections with other EU-funded projects. These collaborations enrich our project's landscape, fueling cross-pollination of ideas and accelerating progress. From the outset, we've been proactive in forging these partnerships, realizing that the collective intelligence of multiple projects can lead to transformative outcomes. Our partners have already started to cultivate these alliances and our project has engaged with a diverse array of projects, each contributing their unique perspectives and innovative approaches. This interconnectedness is not just about expanding project's network; it's about creating a tapestry of knowledge that benefits all involved. More specifically, Smart Droplets actively engaged in joint activities with other EU-funded initiatives and projects during the reporting period. This collaborative ethos yielded remarkable outcomes, with two of our esteemed partners leading the charge. In March 2023, Wageningen University & Research (WUR) orchestrated a workshop in partnership with the **H2020 Optima project**. This dynamic session fostered discussions on shared objectives and synergies, paving the way for a productive collaboration. Equally noteworthy, VLF contributed to the spirit of partnership by presenting the Smart Droplets project at the **Crack Sense project** event in May 2023. This presentation not only showcased our project's potential but also opened avenues for future collaboration possibilities. Moreover, our project made a significant mark at the **agROBOfood Network Event** in Athens, Greece, held from May 11th to 12th, 2023. By collaborating with other pioneering EU-funded projects—such as **Rob4Crops, CoRoSect, SoftGrip, and FlexiGroBots**—they showcased their advancements and address the obstacles involved in engaging with communities and implementing agricultural robotics.

Furthermore, to increase Smart Droplets outreach, the project will participate in the upcoming Synergy Days event, scheduled to take place in Thessaloniki from October 4th to 5th, 2023. As a testament to our commitment to continuous collaboration and innovation, Smart Droplets eagerly joins this event, which constitutes an exceptional platform to foster new beginnings and forge meaningful connections. Dedicated to connecting digital innovators within the European agri-food sector, the Synergy Days represent a significant milestone. The event is set to feature a diverse array of workshops organized by various EU projects (almost 30 EU-funded projects will participate in the Synergy Days Event), alongside comprehensive technical sessions.

Figure 59: EU-Funded Projects at the Synergy Days Event

3.4. EC Tools

Smart Droplets will take advantage of several of the tools offered by the European Commission to support dissemination (D), exploitation (E) and communication (C) of the project’s results (Figure 60).

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Figure 60: Channels and Value EC tools for Smart Droplets

4. Monitoring and Evaluation

To ensure an accurate gauge of the Smart Droplets project's evolution and achievements, a well-defined set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) serves as our compass. These KPIs are not just theoretical benchmarks; they offer measurable targets that underpin ongoing monitoring and evaluation. This section elucidates our approach to tracking progress within the dissemination and communication sphere, laying out a clear framework through tables that encapsulate specific KPIs and corresponding targets. A closer examination of KPIs reveals their essential role as quantifiable signposts, guiding our assessment of project trajectory. Within the realm of dissemination and communication endeavors, we've carefully mapped out KPIs that correspond to the diverse facets of our engagement.

A robust methodology underscores the significance of scrutinizing the execution of our D&C activities to ensure the realization of our project's objectives. This methodology covers not only the identified KPIs but also extends its reach to encompass potential barriers that might transcend our direct influence. Additionally, it incorporates reporting and monitoring KPIs, mitigates potential risks, and acknowledges the importance of accounting for gender-related variations.

A visual depiction, as illustrated in Annexes L,M,N outlines our comprehensive approach to monitoring and evaluation. Our KPIs were meticulously crafted during the project's proposal phase and were subsequently solidified in the Grant Agreement (GA). To further cement our collective commitment, a comprehensive event planning, synergy identification and publications planning document was collaboratively developed, and then disseminated among all partners. The feedback from this concerted engagement, coupled with the distinct competencies each partner brings to the table, forms the basis for assigning specific KPIs to respective entities. This allocation process has been endorsed by our project coordinator and extensively shared with all stakeholders for validation.

A continuous rhythm of progress assessment ensures that we remain on course. This cadence encompasses regular monthly reporting, in-depth analysis of social media analytics, and sustained participation in events that foster synergies. These ongoing contributions, coupled with the insights we glean from the synergy identification process, converge in a bi-annual evaluation. This assessment informs us if we're on track and ready to align our strategies with our objectives, or if adjustments are warranted to steer our course towards a successful outcome.

4.1. KPIs

KPIs are vital benchmarks for achieving project goals, enabling progress assessment and corrective actions. In Smart Droplets, KPIs encompass tools, activities, channels, and audience reach. Within the Smart Droplets framework, a clear distinction is made between dissemination KPIs and communication KPIs. Dissemination KPIs primarily revolve around the seamless transfer of knowledge and the description of results, ensuring they are readily accessible for practical use or future reference. On the other hand, communication KPIs take center stage in our efforts to inform, promote, and share the transformative impact and benefits of the project with society at large. By categorizing and tracking these distinct aspects, our KPIs enable us to finely tune our strategies, ensuring that the dissemination and communication facets of Smart Droplets are aligned for maximum effectiveness.

6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target
D1	Co-organization of events	
D1.1	Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid)	10
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	6
D1.3	"Spotlight on..."Live & On-Demand webinars	6
D1.4	Smart Droplets Solution Showcase and final event	1
D1.5	50 hours of physical and online training content	50
D2	Scientific and technical outreach	
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	5
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	5
D2.3	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	12
D2.4	Competition events (hackathons)	2
D3	Networking and synergies and liaison activities	
D3.1	Representation in WGs	3
D3.2	Representation in alliances	5
D3.3	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	10
D4	Policy measures and standardization efforts	
D4.1	Sets of standardization recommendations	2
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	5
D5	Ecosystem building	
D5.1	MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups	20
D5.2	MoUs/ Lols signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up	5
D5.3	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI	5

Figure 61: Dissemination KPIs

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#	Communication KPIs	Target
C1	Full Branding & Web Design	
C1.1	Printable brand book	1
C1.2	Website	1
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6
C1.4	Posters	3
C1.5	Brochures	3
C1.6	Project factsheet	3
C1.7	Notebook	1
C1.8	Roll-up	1
C1.9	Folder	1
C1.10	Banner	1
C1.11	Stickers	1
C1.12	Virtual background	1
C1.13	Social Media template	1
C2	Digital & Social Media	
C2.1	Unique website pageviews	5000
C2.2	No. of views/ downloads	450
C2.3	Blog posts and Social media posts	250
C2.4	No. of Social media followers	1500
C2.5	No. of newsletter subscribers	500
C2.6	Newsletter (quarterly edition)	14
C2.7	Average click-to-open rate	20-30%
C3	Press Outreach & Event Planning	
C3.1	Press releases	10
C3.2	Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio, magazines, newspaper)	5
C3.3	Articles in agriculture and industry magazines	10
C3.4	2 Digital Ag 360° podcast learning series/seasons	14

Figure 62: Communication KPIs

4.1.1. KPIs per reporting period

Furthermore, the KPIs will be distributed between the three reporting periods (M1-M12, M13-M24, M25-M42) in which the DEC plan will be also updated. Figures 64-65 includes a breakdown of the expected KPIs and their targets to be achieved during each reporting period. This will be a preliminary plan that is foreseen and is subject to change and updated by each deliverable based on projections of the project activities and the scope of each partner. Furthermore, the reporting mechanism will help maintain accountability and achieve these targets.

Figure 63: Methodology for the division the KPIs

6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	M1 - M12	M13 - M24	M25 - M42
D1	Co-organization of events				
D1.1	Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid)	10	1	3	6
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	6	-	4	2
D1.3	"Spotlight on..."Live & On-Demand webinars	6	1	2	3
D1.4	Smart Droplets Solution Showcase and final event	1			1
D1.5	50 hours of physical and online training content	50	-	25	25
D2	Scientific and technical outreach				
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	5	-	2	3
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	5	-	2	3
D2.3	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	12	-	-	12
D2.4	Competition events (hackathons)	2	-	1	1
D3	Networking and synergies and liaison activities				
D3.1	Representation in WGs	3	-	2	1
D3.2	Representation in alliances	5	-	3	2
D3.3	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	10	-	5	5
D4	Policy measures and standardization efforts				
D4.1	Sets of standardization recommendations	2	-	1	1
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	5	-	2	3
D5	Ecosystem building				
D5.1	MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups	20	-	10	10
D5.2	MoUs/ Lols signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up	5	-	2	3
D5.3	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI	5	-	4	1

Figure 64: Dissemination KPIs per reporting period

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#	Communication KPIs	Target	M1 - M12	M13 - M24	M25 - M42
C1	Full Branding & Web Design				
C1.1	Printable brand book	1	1		
C1.2	Website	1	1		
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6	6		
C1.4	Posters	3	3		
C1.5	Brochures	3	3		
C1.6	Project factsheet	3	3		
C1.7	Notebook	1	1		
C1.8	Roll-up	1	1		
C1.9	Folder	1	1		
C1.10	Banner	1	1		
C1.11	Stickers	1	1		
C1.12	Virtual background	1	1		
C1.13	Social Media template	1	1		
C2	Digital & Social Media				
C2.1	Unique website pageviews	5000	1000	3000	5000
C2.2	No. of views/ downloads	450	-	50	400
C2.3	Blog posts and Social media posts	250	50	100	100
C2.4	No. of Social media followers	1500	700	1200	1500
C2.5	No. of newsletter subscribers	500	100	300	500
C2.6	Newsletter (quarterly edition)	14	4	4	6
C2.7	Average click-to-open rate	20-30%		20-30%	
C3	Press Outreach & Event Planning				
C3.1	Press releases	10	2	4	4
C3.2	Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio, magazines,	5	1	2	2
C3.3	Articles in agriculture and industry magazines	10	1	4	5
C3.4	2 Digital Ag 360° podcast learning series/seasons	14	-	7	7

Figure 65: Communication KPIs per reporting period

The first reporting period of the project was fundamental for establishing connections and building interest around the project and was used to:

- **Stakeholder Mapping:** Identifying and comprehending stakeholders and their needs that demand our attention.
- **Strategic Branding:** Crafting the project's website, visual identity, communication materials, and dynamic social media platforms.
- **Collaborative Decision-Making Protocol:** Laying the groundwork for transparent event selection, publication decisions, and the identification of fruitful synergies.
- **Engagement:** Initiating collaborations with parallel projects and initiatives for a wider sphere of influence.
- **Visible Presence:** Active participation in events and dissemination via press releases and informative newsletters.
- **Unified Communication:** Ensuring all partners are well-versed in communication channels, templates, and protocols.
- **Scientific Outreach Enhancement:** Elevating our commitment to augment the project's influence and impact within scientific communities.

As we stride into the next reporting period, our efforts will intensify, embarking on:

- **Enhanced Event Landscape:** Orchestrating a series of compelling events and demonstrations to attract a growing community of followers and showcase Smart Droplets solutions.
- **Synergy Formation:** Forge strategic ties with related projects and associations, amplifying our impact and reach.
- **Industry Attraction:** Garner attention from industry associations, investors, and potential partners, bolstering our drive for refinement, commercialization, and scalability.
- **Democratizing Knowledge:** Disseminating the wealth of knowledge generated within the project through the creation of comprehensive training content.

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- Press Outreach Advancement:** Bolstering our proactive engagement in press outreach, we're set to further amplify our impact. This entails skillfully crafted press releases, captivating interviews, and insightful articles featured in pertinent magazines. Through these channels, we aim not only to disseminate project achievements to a wider audience but also to stimulate a deeper understanding and appreciation of Smart Droplets' transformative potential within relevant industry spheres.

This upcoming phase promises a heightened level of activity and engagement as we drive forward, capitalizing on our initial momentum, and advancing our pursuit of even greater impact and innovation in the agricultural sector.

4.1.2. KPIs per partner

The Smart Droplets project operates under a collaborative framework where the dissemination and communication efforts outlined in the DEC plan are collectively undertaken by each consortium partner. Acknowledging the diversity of expertise within our consortium, we have strategically assigned KPIs to individual partners, delineated in Figures 66 and 67. A balanced distribution has been achieved by aligning planned events and identified synergies.

The list of allocated KPIs has been rigorously validated by the project coordinator and subsequently shared with all partners. Should any partner encounter challenges in fulfilling their assigned KPIs, a collaborative discussion will be initiated to explore alternative solutions. Changes, if deemed necessary, will be duly documented in subsequent iterations of the DEC plan.

Collectively, all partners play a pivotal role in project communication and result dissemination. Tailored to the unique strengths, experiences, and resource allocations of each partner, the KPIs and targets have been meticulously outlined. These individualized tables are integrated within each partner's reporting sheet for ready reference. In our relentless pursuit to share project outcomes and amplify impact through diverse expertise and networks, this concerted effort ensures that our goals are effectively communicated and realized. The detailed breakdown of KPIs per partner is presented in the ensuing tables.

Dissemination KPIs		Target	AUA	WU	EUT	VLF	FSH	AGC	AFL	AGROMA SA	FEMAC
#	PMs		12	8	4	3	52	4,5	9	5	4
D1 Co-organization of events											
D1.1	Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid)	10	2	2			2	1	2	1	
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	6			3				3		
D1.3	'Spotlight on...'Live & On-Demand webinars	6	2	2			2				
D1.4	Smart Droplets Solution Showcase and final event	1					1				
D1.5	50 hours of physical and online training content	50	15	15	10				10		
D2 Scientific and technical outreach											
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	5	2	2	1						
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	5	1	1	2	1					
D2.3	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	12					12				
D2.4	Competition events (hackathons)	2	1	1							
D3 Networking and synergies and liaison activities											
D3.1	Representation in WGs	3						1	1		1
D3.2	Representation in alliances	5	1	1	1		1		1		
D3.3	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	10	5	2			2		1		
D4 Policy measures and standardization efforts											
D4.1	Sets of standardization recommendations	2					2				
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	5	1	1	1				1		1
D5 Ecosystem building											
D5.1	MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups/projects	20	4		2	2	4	2	2	2	2
D5.2	MoUs/ Lols signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up	5	1				1	1	1	1	
D5.3	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI	5	1			2			2		

Figure 66: Dissemination KPIs per partner

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Communication KPIs		Target	AUA	WU	EUT	VLF	FSH	AGC	AFL	AGROMA SA	FEMAC
#	PMs		12	8	4	3	52	4.5	9	5	4
C1	Full Branding & Web Design										
C1.1	Printable brand book	1					1				
C1.2	Website	1					1				
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6					6				
C1.4	Posters	3					3				
C1.5	Brochures	3					3				
C1.6	Project factsheet	3					3				
C1.7	Notebook	1					1				
C1.8	Roll-up	1					1				
C1.9	Folder	1					1				
C1.10	Banner	1					1				
C1.11	Stickers	1					1				
C1.12	Virtual background	1					1				
C1.13	Social Media template	1					1				
C2	Digital & Social Media										
C2.1	Unique website pageviews	5000					5000				
C2.2	No. of views/ downloads	450					450				
C2.3	Blog posts and Social media posts	250	10	10	10	10	170	10	10	10	10
C2.4	No. of Social media followers	1500					1500				
C2.5	No. of newsletter subscribers	500					500				
C2.6	Newsletter (quarterly edition)	14					14				
C2.7	Average click-to-open rate	20-30%					20-30%				
C3	Press Outreach & Event Planning										
C3.1	Press releases published to the website	10					10				
C3.2	Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio, magazines, newspaper)	5	1		1		1		1		1
C3.3	Articles in agriculture and industry magazines	10	2	1		1	3		1		2
C3.4	2 Digital Ag 360° podcast learning series/seasons	14					14				

Figure 67: Communication KPIs per partner

4.2. Reporting Tools

Event and communication reporting

During the first months of the project, the seamless execution of timely reporting and effective monitoring for all dissemination and communication activities was of paramount importance. To facilitate this process, FSH devised an online form, exemplified below, to systematically gather input from our consortium partners. This form was designed to capture the intricacies of their undertaken measures while ensuring a streamlined reporting structure. Within this framework, partners were entrusted with the responsibility of furnishing comprehensive feedback on their dissemination and communication endeavors on a monthly basis. This practice allowed for a meticulous tracking of project progress and a real-time assessment of the alignment between planned activities and actual implementation.

The screenshot shows the 'Smart Droplets- Communication & Dissemination Activity Report' form. It features a header with the Smart Droplets logo and a greeting to partners. The form is divided into several sections:

- Partner Selection:** Radio buttons for VLF, AGC, AFL, AGROMA SA, FEMAC, and FSH.
- Type of activity:** Radio buttons for various activities like 'Organisation of a conference', 'Press release', 'Exhibitions', etc.
- Date of the activity:** A date picker field.
- Channels used:** A text area for listing promotional channels.
- Type and Size of audience:** Radio buttons for audience type and a text area for audience size.
- Coverage level:** Radio buttons for Local, Regional, National, Cross-border, and EU.
- Feedback and Impact:** A text area for providing feedback.

Figure 68: Smart Droplets old reporting form

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However, as the project evolved, it was recognized the need for an even more refined and collaborative approach to KPI reporting. As a result, a transition was made from the initial online form to a more interactive and adaptable tool, constructed using Google Spreadsheets. This solution fostered enhanced communication and collaboration between partners, facilitating a more robust data exchange process for the measured outcomes. This strategic shift empowered partners to provide granular insights into their progress. This iterative process ensures that KPIs remain aligned with project objectives, ultimately contributing to more effective impact measurement and strategic decision-making. Still, each month, all partners are requested to update this online inventory of any communication or dissemination activities and deposit corresponding promoting material such as photos, reports, etc. in a designated folder. This procedure has proven that it reinforces accountability and engagement with the dissemination and communication process. FSH is responsible for monitoring the KPIs on a monthly basis and give updates to the rest of the partners at relevant meetings. In case, significant, or repeated deviations are recorded from certain partners, the coordinator will be officially informed. Deviations will have to be justified, discussed among partners, and changes on the DEC strategy will be reported on the updated versions of the DEC plan. In total, this online google spreadsheet has been developed and uploaded on the project's shared Drive and is available to all partners. The spreadsheet includes the following:

- **Sheet 1: Instructions** - The workbook provides instructions, a description of the KPIs, the breakdown per reporting period and a sheet dedicated to each partner. In each spreadsheet, the respective participating organisation can see the KPIs assigned to them, and the dissemination and communication activities that need to be reported, accordingly, per month of action.

Instructions
1. This file has been designed for reporting dissemination & communication activities that relate to the KPIs described in the GA and the distributed targets per partner .
The first page provides the total KPI targets and the breakdown per reporting period.
2. Each partner has a dedicated sheet with three tables:
a. KPI distribution: - The overall target for each KPI per partner.
b. Dissemination Activities (e.g. events, synergies, publications): - Please use the drop down menu to select the KPI category, then provide the name, date and link. - Please indicate if the activity should be considered a joint activity (external to the consortium), and if yes, please indicate with whom.
c. Communications Activities (e.g. social media, interviews): - Please use the drop down menu to select the type of publication or communication channel, then provide the date and a link where it can be found.
3. In case the dissemination/communication activity does not fall under the already existing KPI categories, fill in the drop-down menu with the option " Other ", while filling-in all the other columns.
4. Click on links for each month to upload pictures or relevant materials (e.g., agenda, presentations) from events that may be used for dissemination and communication purposes.
Please note: * we suggest posts come from your organization's social media account, rather than a personal account and that you tag Smart Droplets * please include the dates and links

Figure 69: Instruction for the new reporting form

- **Sheet 2: KPI Clarification** - To minimise confusion regarding the scope of each KPI and to help partners decide which KPI their activity corresponds to a dedicated sheet is included in the reporting workbook.

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The focus is on the dissemination KPIs which have greater ambiguity. All descriptions have been validated by the Project Coordinator

#	Dissemination KPIs	Target	M1 - M12	M13 - M24	M25 - M42	Clarifications
D1	Participation and co-organization of events					
D1.1	Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid)	10	1	3	6	Events organized or co-organized by the partners to analyze market segments / or provide insight of the industry relevant to the project and partners' expertise.
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	6	-	4	2	Events open for everyone to visit the demo areas and to understand the importance of our project.
D1.3	"Spotlight on..." Live & On-Demand webinars	6	1	2	3	Webinars organized or co-organized by the partners that are broadcasted both live and on-demand in fields that align with the project's and partners' areas of expertise.
D1.4	Smart Droplets Solution Showcase and final event	1	-	-	1	The final event of the project aiming to present the results of the project.
D1.5	50 hours of physical and online training content	50	-	25	25	Physical and online training content produced available after the project is due.
D2	Scientific and technical outreach					
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	5	-	2	3	Scholarly papers and conference contributions that have undergone evaluation by field experts.
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	5	-	2	3	Publication of technical briefs in renowned magazines or publications that specialize in the fields of Robotics, Data, and AI.
D2.3	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	12	-	-	12	Project's public deliverables available for the general public.
D2.4	Competition events (hackathons)	2	-	1	1	Hackathons, competitive events, held within a specific period aiming to generate results that can be utilised by the project.
D3	Networking and synergies and liaison activities					
D3.1	Representation in WGs	3	-	2	1	Establish connections with and participate in working groups dedicated to project-specific topics.
D3.2	Representation in alliances	5	-	3	2	Establish connections and partnerships with alliances to foster collaboration, share resources etc.
D3.3	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	10	-	5	5	Engage in collaborative endeavors with EU initiatives/projects to leverage collective expertise, share best practices, and maximize the impact of efforts in the field of AI, data, and robotics.
D4	Policy measures and standardization efforts					
D4.1	Sets of standardization recommendations	2	-	1	1	Develop comprehensive sets of recommendations for standardization in order to guide and promote the widespread adoption of AI, Robotics, and Data technologies in agriculture.
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	5	-	2	3	Collaborate with digital agriculture technology initiatives and movements to issue joint press releases and statements, aimed at raising awareness, advocating for policy measures, and highlighting the potential benefits of AI, Robotics, and Data technologies in the agricultural sector.
D5	Ecosystem building					
D5.1	MoUs/ Lots with industry associations & groups	20	-	10	10	Establish agreements (Memorandum of Understanding / Letter of Interest) with industry associations and groups to foster collaboration, knowledge exchange, and joint efforts in promoting the adoption and utilization of the Smart Droplets solution.
D5.2	MoUs/ Lots signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up	5	-	2	3	Forming nonbinding agreements (Memorandum of Understanding / Letter of Interest) with investors and other potential partners to secure support and resources for refining, commercializing, and expanding the Smart Droplets solution.
D5.3	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI	5	-	4	1	Establish connections with Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) that are associated with AI, Data, and Robotics to facilitate collaboration, leverage expertise, and ensure sustained uptake of the Smart Droplets solution beyond the duration of public funding.
#	Communication KPIs	Target	M1 - M12	M13 - M24	M25 - M42	
C1	Full Branding & Web Design					
C1.1	Printable brand book	1	1			
C1.2	Website	1	1			
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6	6			
C1.4	Posters	3	3			
C1.5	Brochures	3	3			
C1.6	Project factsheet	3	3			

Figure 70: Clarifications for the KPIs

- Sheets 3 through 9: Individual Partner Reporting Sheets** – A set of distinct reporting sheets has been crafted for each consortium partner. These tailored sheets serve as a user-friendly and efficient platform for documenting their executed dissemination and communication activities. The process has been streamlined for ease of use and accuracy. Within these sheets, a user-friendly drop-down menu is integrated under the KPI category tab. This intuitive feature empowers partners to conveniently select the relevant category for their executed dissemination or communication action. Subsequent fields facilitate the input of essential information, encompassing data specifics, activity names, associated links, and other pertinent details. To facilitate differentiation between no reporting and non-participation in relevant activities, partners can indicate "Nothing to report" if they have no dissemination or communication activities to report. Additionally, to support visual documentation, each month features clickable links to designated folders for partners to upload photos and other pertinent materials such as agendas, presentations, and minutes. These resources may be leveraged for reporting, dissemination, or communication purposes. This comprehensive framework ensures a holistic approach to tracking, documenting, and sharing project activities. This structured format enhances the clarity and consistency of reporting, ensuring that all vital information is accurately captured. The user-friendly design encourages partners to comprehensively document their activities, fostering an environment of collaboration and data accuracy.

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September 2022										
Photos and other material										
Dissemination KPI					Communication KPI					
KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link	
Nothing to report					<input type="checkbox"/>	Nothing to report				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				

October 2022										
Photos and other material										
Dissemination KPI					Communication KPI					
KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link	
Nothing to report					<input type="checkbox"/>	Nothing to report				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				

November 2022										
Photos and other material										
Dissemination KPI					Communication KPI					
KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link	Joint Action (YES)	If yes, with whom?	KPI Category	Date	Name of Activity	Link	
Nothing to report					<input type="checkbox"/>	Nothing to report				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				
▼				<input type="checkbox"/>		▼				

Figure 71: Clarifications for the KPIs

Finally, a reminder is sent to each partner at the end of the month reminding them to complete the reporting form by the second week of the following month. The form is also available on project's google drive, enabling partners to go back and review or add missing activities and it also allows for different members from the same organisation to provide input without redundancy. FSH monitors the reporting form monthly to keep track of engagement, and on a six month basis consolidates the results of the reporting forms and evaluates them next to the KPIs. The findings of these reports will serve to monitor targets and inform DEC strategies, enabling pivoting when necessary or to inform partners when additional effort is required.

4.3. Monitoring Tool for KPI tracking

To precision and efficiency in monitoring the KPIs, FSH has meticulously developed and deployed a dedicated monitoring tool to track the progress of our partners' achieved KPIs. This robust tool is constructed utilizing the capabilities of Google Spreadsheets, enabling real-time monitoring of KPI progress across reporting periods and partners. Figure 72 displays the comprehensive monitoring spreadsheet, where dissemination and communication KPIs are thoughtfully categorized into three distinct reporting periods. Within each reporting period, two validation statuses have been established to ensure both the timely completion of KPIs and the prompt implementation of mitigation measures, should the need arise.

#	Communication KPIs	M13-M12			Status	M13-M24			Status	M25-M42			Sum	Target	Status
		1st check	Final check			1st check	Final check			1st check	Final check				
C1	Full Branding & Web Design														
C1.1	Printable brand book	1	1		Completed								1	1	
C1.2	Website	1	1		Completed								1	1	
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6	6		Completed								6	6	
C1.4	Posters	3	3		Completed								3	3	
C1.5	Brochures	3	3		Completed								3	3	
C1.6	Project factsheet	3	3		Completed								3	3	
C1.7	Notebook	1	1		Completed								1	1	
C1.8	Roll-up	1	1		Completed								1	1	
C1.9	Folder	1	1		Completed								1	1	
C1.10	Banner	1	1		Completed								1	1	
C1.11	Stickers	1	1		Completed								1	1	
C1.12	Virtual background	1	1		Completed								1	1	
C1.13	Social Media template	1	1		Completed								1	1	
C2	Digital & Social Media														
C2.1	Unique website pageviews	1000	420	917	Ongoing	3000				5000			1337	5000	
C2.2	No. of views/ downloads												0	450	

Figure 72: Monitoring tool for the KPIs

Moreover, within the same integrated spreadsheet file, individual sheets are thoughtfully allocated to each partner. These dedicated sheets are meticulously updated by FSH based on partners' monthly reports,

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consolidating their achievements and contributions. This meticulous approach further enhances transparency, collaboration, and accountability, streamlining the process of assessing our collective progress and promptly addressing any potential challenges.

#	KPI	TARGET							
Dissemination KPIs									
D1	Co-organization of events								
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	3							
D2	Scientific and technical outreach								
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	1							
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	2							
D3	Networking and synergies and liaison activities								
D3.2	Representation in alliances	1							
D4	Policy measures and standardization efforts								
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	1							
D5	Ecosystem building								
D5.1	MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups/projects	2							
Communication KPIs									
C2	Digital & Social Media								
C2.3	Blog posts and Social media posts	10							
C3	Press Outreach & Event Planning								
C3.2	Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio, magazines, newspaper)	1							

Figure 73: Monitoring tool for each partner

The current progress of the Dissemination and Communication KPIs in relation to the targets set for the initial reporting period is outlined in Figures 74 and 75. It's important to note that the current status is based on the input provided by partners through the reporting form, which may not encompass the entirety of activity engagement. In the table, the status **Completed** indicates the respective KPIs have been successfully achieved, reflecting the notable progress made in meeting the targets during the first reporting period. Also, the **Ongoing** status signifies the KPIs that are well on track to being achieved by the conclusion of the first reporting period. Conversely, the **red boxes** highlight KPIs that require heightened attention and effort to ensure successful attainment. This comprehensive overview aids in gauging the alignment of our current progress with the predetermined targets.

#	Dissemination KPIs	M1-M12	1st check	Final check	Status
D1	Participation and co-organization of events				
D1.1	Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid)	1	0	2	Completed
D1.2	Open Days (3 showcase events per demo)	-			
D1.3	"Spotlight on..."Live & On-Demand webinars	1	0	0	Uncompleted
D1.4	Smart Droplets Solution Showcase and final event	-			
D1.5	50 hours of physical and online training content	-	2	2	Completed
D2	Scientific and technical outreach				
D2.1	Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions	-	1	1	Completed
D2.2	Tech briefs in Robotic, Data & AI magazines/ publications	-			
D2.3	Number of Publicly Available Deliverables	-			
D2.4	Competition events (hackathons)	-			
D3	Networking and synergies and liaison activities				
D3.1	Representation in WGs	-			
D3.2	Representation in alliances	-	-	1	Completed
D3.3	Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects	-	-	2	Completed
D4	Policy measures and standardization efforts				
D4.1	Sets of standardization recommendations	-			
D4.2	Joint press releases/ statements with digital agriculture technology initiatives & movements	-			
D5	Ecosystem building				
D5.1	MoUs/ Lols with industry associations & groups	-			
D5.2	MoUs/ Lols signed with investors and other potential partners to drive further fine-tuning, commercialization, and scaling up	-			
D5.3	Connections established with DIHs connected to AI	-			

Figure 74: Completed, Ongoing and Uncompleted Dissemination KPIs

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#	Communication KPIs	M1-M12	1st check	Final check	Status
C1	Full Branding & Web Design				
C1.1	Printable brand book	1	1		Completed
C1.2	Website	1	1		Completed
C1.3	Social Media accounts	6	6		Completed
C1.4	Posters	3	3		Completed
C1.5	Brochures	3	3		Completed
C1.6	Project factsheet	3	3		Completed
C1.7	Notebook	1	1		Completed
C1.8	Roll-up	1	1		Completed
C1.9	Folder	1	1		Completed
C1.10	Banner	1	1		Completed
C1.11	Stickers	1	1		Completed
C1.12	Virtual background	1	1		Completed
C1.13	Social Media template	1	1		Completed
C2	Digital & Social Media				
C2.1	Unique website pageviews	1000	420	917	Ongoing
C2.2	No. of views/ downloads				
C2.3	Blog posts & social media posts	50	73	169	Completed
C2.4	No. of Social media followers	700	294	979	Completed
C2.5	No. of newsletter subscribers	100	35	101	Completed
C2.6	Newsletter (quarterly edition)	4	2	1	Ongoing
C2.7	Average click-to-open rate				
C3	Press Outreach & Event Planning				
C3.1	Press releases	2	1		Ongoing
C3.2	Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio)	1	0	1	Completed
C3.3	Articles in agriculture and industry magazines	1	0	0	Uncompleted
C3.4	2 Digital Ag 360° podcast learning series/seasons	-			

Figure 75: Completed, Ongoing and Uncompleted Communication KPIs

Action Points – KPIs that have been achieved and exceeded

Many of the KPI targets have been met already (e.g., brochures, project factsheets, posters) or exceeded (e.g., Market & industry events, Representation in alliances, Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects social media followers, newsletter subscribers, Blog posts & social media posts). For KPI targets that have not been met specific action points have been identified. More specifically:

- **D1.1 Market & industry events (online/ offline/ hybrid):** Two of our partners presented the Smart Droplets project in Market and industry events. EUT presented the project in the "Technological infrastructures for the digitalization of the agricultural sector", in Lleida, Spain, on the 23rd of March 2023, while AGROMA presented Smart Droplets to their commercial partners at their premises in Veria, on the 12th of May 2023.
- **D1.5 50 hours of physical and online training content:** Our partner WUR, started already generating useful training content, by implementing a workshop with the Agrokoncernas (16th of February 2023), where Smart Droplets technologies were presented as well as and by participating in the Seminar at Plant Sciences at Wageningen University, where the Climate Resilient Nitrogen Management with Reinforcement Learning and Crop Models was presented.
- **D2.1 Peer-reviewed papers & conferences contributions:** WUR presented 2 posters, one in Optimizing Nitrogen Management in Winter Wheat: A Reinforcement Learning Approach with Crop Growth Models at the AgMIP9 on the 26th of June 2023 at Columbia University in New York, NY, USA and one more poster with title "Integrating process-based models and machine learning for crop yield prediction" at the Int'l Conference on Machine Learning, in New York presented, regarding on July 23.
- **D3.2 Representation in alliances:** Our partner VLF, on the 26th of May 2023, presented Smart Droplets project and its data management platform in the Agrifood Working Group of AIOTI.

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- **D3.3 Joint activities with EU initiatives/ projects:** Two of our partners conducted joint activities with other EU-funded project during the reporting period. More specifically, WUR conducted a workshop with H2020 project Optima, on the 7th of March 2023, to discuss commonalities between the two projects in order to build a fruitful collaboration, as well as VLF presented on the 26th of May 2023, the Smart Droplets project in the event of Crack Sense project for the purpose of possible collaboration in future. Furthermore, our project represented in the agROBOfood Network Event, which took place in Athens, Greece from the 11th to 12th of May 2023, where it participated with other EU-funded projects (Robs4Crops, CoRoSect, SoftGrip, FlexiGroBots) to showcase their advancements and address the obstacles involved in engaging with communities and implementing agricultural robotics.
- **C1 Full Branding & Web Design:** FSH developed all the relevant material during the first 6 months and more specifically 1 Printable brand book, 1 Website, 6 Social Media accounts, 3 Posters, 3 Brochures, 3 Project factsheet, 1 Notebook, 1 Roll-up, 1 Folder, 1 Banner, 1 Stickers, 1 Virtual background, 1 social media template.
- **C2.3 Blog posts & social media posts:** All the Smart Droplets partners contributed in order to exceed this KPI, driving to the creation of engaging and interesting content which led to several re-tweets and re-posts from several interested parties.
- **C2.4 No. of Social media followers:** As mentioning above, the development of high-quality content had an impact also in the social media followers, exceeding the initial goal of 700 followers for 279. LinkedIn was the major social media account with the most followers, followed by Twitter, Facebook, YouTube and SlideShare.
- **C2.5 No. of newsletter subscribers:** During the current reporting period, 3 newsletters have been published, while the 4th one is going to be published in the upcoming weeks. The material had more informative character, offering readers a comprehensive comprehension of the technologies integrated into the project and their anticipated effects in the upcoming years as well as their multi-level benefits that they offer.
- **C3.2 Speeches / Interviews/ Participation in media (TV, radio):** Our partner from FSH were live on the TV show “Smart Economy” by TV100 in Thessaloniki Greece, explaining how Smart Droplets aims to contribute to a more sustainable future in farming, with the reduction of chemicals use, by combining data and technology.

Action Points – KPIs that are on track

- **C2.1 Unique website pageviews:** At the upcoming Synergy Days event in October our project partners will have the opportunity to discuss with the attendees and magnetise their interest, while the main source of information will be the website for further information.
- **C2.6 Newsletter (quarterly edition):** The 4th newsletter is drafted, and it is expecting to be published in the upcoming weeks.
- **C3.1 Press releases:** The second press release is expecting to be published after the participation of the project in the Synergy Days event as well as after the completion of the project meeting, in October in The Netherlands.

Action Points – KPIs Requiring Additional Attention

- **D1.3 “Spotlight on... “Live & On-Demand webinars:** This will be included as a topic of October’s project meeting, in order to begin discussion and determine an approach for participating and/or organising such webinars.
- **C3.3 Articles in agriculture and industry magazines:** Partners responsible for achieving this KPI will be contacted to determine whether they have any content for an agriculture or industry magazine article and to plan and map the specific timing of these publications.

5. Exploitation

A series of commercial and non-commercial Key Exploitable Results (KERs) will be fabricated within the Smart Droplets project. This chapter, building upon the dedicated Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5) developed in the previous months (M6), expanding the preliminary results, as presented in the Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1), by providing a concrete roadmap for the duration of the project and beyond, will delve into these results, potential pathways for their exploitation and KPIs for monitoring their impact. A dedicated Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v2 (D6.5) will be developed by M18, to bring up to date this updated version of the plan, as well as the concrete roadmap, by ameliorating the identification and highlighting processes of measures, towards capitalizing on and ensuring sustainability of Smart Droplets results. This continuous rationalisation of the plan reflects to the agile approach implemented by the consortium, throughout project's lifetime, aiming at the tangibility of the accordance between project's outputs and targeted stakeholders' needs, contributing this way to the mitigation of the Risk No. 11 of Critical risks & risk management strategy.

5.1. Key Exploitable Results

During the Proposal Preparation Phase, Smart Droplets had foreseen the development of a set of Key Exploitable Results (KERs). This sub-chapter reflects as a sequel of the former section of the Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1) imprinting the identified seven final key exploitable results, whilst respecting and aligning with the processes and measures described within the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5). Figure 76 imprints the seven results, as identified in the Proposal Preparation Phase and Grant Agreement phase, whereas the Figure 77 describes, more detailed, each result, regardless of form or nature, tangibility or intangibility, commercialisation, or non-commercialisation, who is responsible for it, who it will benefit, as well as its Unique Value Proposition (UVP), as captured in the in the initial plan of the Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1).

Figure 76: Smart Droplets KERs

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Figure 77: Smart Droplets KERs

5.2. Identification of new exploitable results

While the initial capturing of Smart Droplets' KERs has already been initiated, leaving only the validation phase, towards the development of the list of final KERs, to follow (M14), the innovation – oriented character of the project pushes the possibility of identifying additional KERs, by the consortium, approaching certainty, demanding this way, a comprehensive, iterative, and continuing process for compiling Smart Droplets KERs'. For this reason, the following methodology, consisting of 5 steps, has been established, as depicted in Figure 78.

Figure 78: Methodology for the identification and inclusion of a new KER

Aiming at empowering their continuous capturing, monitoring and management during project's lifecycle, the development of a template of Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue (Annex O) is foreseen. This Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue will be utilised as an identification tool, both for the validation of these KERs, either commercial or non-commercial, as well as for the mapping of new non-commercial KERs, that may arise any time during the project. This Catalogue aims to include both, commercial and non – commercial, tangible, and intangible outcomes, that present a potential to be exploited after the end of project's lifetime,

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incorporating at the same time, all potential applications (scientific, societal, and economic) and briefly highlight partners' future strategy and intentions. Up to this point, the first initial edition of the Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue v1 has been elaborated, with its validation from the consortium approaching, as mentioned above. Bearing in mind that the compiling Smart Droplets KERs' process holds a continuous character, the Smart Droplets Exploitation, and IP Catalogue, as explained in detailed in the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5) is provisioned to be updated by the consortium three times, during the project timeframe, in a way to follow the timelines of project activities. More specifically, its finetuning shall be expected at the end of each MVP phase (D6.6 in M18 and D6.7 in M30).

In a nutshell, the Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue concludes key information including:

- Description of the exploitable result
- Nature of the exploitable result (tangible, intangible)
- Unique Value Proposition (UVP)
- Status of exploitation (commercial, non-commercial)
- Scope of exploitation (scientific, educational, societal, political and economic)
- Target groups (to whom)
- Means of exploitation
- IPR(s) linked to the KER, if relevant.

5.3. Exploitation pathways

As mentioned in the previous section of the respective chapter, a series of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) will be developed within the Smart Droplets project. Considering that there is no limitation declared in the status of the exploitable result (commercial, non-commercial) the robust catalogue of KERs, namely Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue, includes both commercial and non-commercial KERs and will continue to be adding newly identified non-commercial KERs, during project's lifespan. Regardless of being commercial or non-commercial, the overall objective of each individual KER lies with the provision of solutions to a specific stakeholder problem and adding a unique particular value. This section rises as a follow-up of the preliminary exploitation plan, stated within the Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1), outlining exploitation modalities and paths to bring Smart Droplets results to key stakeholder segments, ensuring sustainability after the project completion.

5.3.1. Non-commercial Exploitation

Having in mind that Smart Droplets identifies, two types of project results – commercial and non-commercial and hence not all results streaming from the project will have a commercial purpose and exploitation on the market, important attention and notice shall be given to the investigation and elaboration of exploitation routes dedicated for non-commercial project results.

A list of potential non-commercial KERs shall include the following:

- publications (papers, books),
- presentations,
- supporting further research activities data,
- specific reports,
- policy papers and recommendations (for revision or creation of a new directives or regulations on EU and/or Member States level)

The exploitation pathways and routes of non – commercial results, may appear on different extends. Either making reference to individual or joint exploitation plan, these non-commercial outcomes encompass a spectrum of dimensions, as indicated in Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5), the including scientific, educational, societal, and political spheres:

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- **Scientific Progress and Reusability:** Within this ambit, the project yields an array of scientific outputs encompassing models, methodologies, prototypes, and datasets. These intellectual contributions, engendered over the project's duration, hold the potential to be harnessed by the wider scientific community for subsequent research endeavors. By facilitating continuity and building upon existing knowledge, these outputs can significantly bolster future scientific undertakings.
- **Policy – Making:** The results gleaned from the project bear the capacity to furnish policymakers and regulatory bodies with empirically grounded insights. Such evidence-based information serves as a cornerstone for formulating novel policies or refining extant ones. The project's findings thereby play an instrumental role in guiding policy decisions that are substantiated by robust empirical data.
- **Educational and Training Synergy:** Certain outcomes arising from the project's endeavors lend themselves to the creation of educational and training modules aimed at diverse audiences including students, professionals, and the broader public. These pedagogical materials not only disseminate project insights but also contribute to enhancing knowledge dissemination and skill acquisition within the relevant domains.
- **Catalysing Standards in Agriculture:** The project's outputs hold the potential to instigate the formulation of fresh benchmarks and standards in domains like agricultural practices and technologies. By virtue of these standards, the broader agricultural landscape can undergo positive transformations and advancements.

In harnessing the scientific breakthroughs pioneered by Smart Droplets, several avenues for exploitation become evident. These encompass:

- i. **Integration into Existing Research Activities:** The integration of these breakthroughs into ongoing research initiatives amplifies their impact and relevance, fostering a dynamic exchange of ideas and approaches.
- ii. **Embarking on Novel Research Collaborations:** Collaborative ventures with third parties present fertile ground for expanding the scope and reach of the project's discoveries, enriching the collective knowledge base.
- iii. **Educational and Training Initiatives:** Academic institutions, especially universities aspiring to augment their appeal and cultivate high-caliber professionals, can draw upon these breakthroughs to devise educational and training programs.

However, it is imperative to acknowledge that certain parameters governing the scientific utilization may be stipulated by private project partners with a vested interest in safeguarding their economic concerns. These restrictions, potentially circumscribing aspects such as temporal utilization, will be pertinent solely to knowledge generated through collaborative efforts between commercial enterprises and research institutions. This measured approach strikes a balance between scientific advancement and safeguarding the economic prerogatives of stakeholders.

5.3.2. Commercial Exploitation

Besides the non – commercial outcomes analysed in the abovementioned section, Smart Droplets holds a set of commercial KERs, as imprinted in the Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue, that present the potential to be commercially exploited, meaning that the seven identified results can be introduced into the general market. These commercial KERs may be introduced to the market ecosystem in any of the following forms of commercial results:

- products (e.g., technologies, platforms, software)
- services (e.g., advisory, consulting services, public services)
- processes (e.g., innovative processes, public processes)
- methodologies (e.g., mathematical, statistical, any research methodologies, data analysis)
- training programs
- data generated during the project, etc.

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Considering that the commercial aspect of the Smart Droplets is of significant importance, investing in high-impact and fruitful exploitation pathways appears necessary. Taking into consideration the basis set for the exploitation plan in both the Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1) and the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5) this section of the respective deliverable highlights the pathways needed to be investigated for an effective exploitation of the Smart Droplets results. These exploitation pathways encompass a Go-to-market strategy, a Value Network analysis, Lean Business Models, and a Funding analysis. All these pathways shall be examined for each individual commercial Smart Droplets KER.

5.3.2.1. Go-to-Market Strategy

The Go-to-Market Strategy constitutes an exploitation pathway of Smart Droplets commercial KERs of paramount importance. When examining the development of an effective Go-to-Market Strategy, a Market Analysis can't be missing from the acquisition. Market Analysis constitutes of an indivisible tool for a high-impact Go-to-Market Strategy, providing insights for the understanding and elaboration of the Go-to-Market Strategy's critical parts. These critical parts consist of the following:

1. Product-market fit: the problem(s) that our solution solves.
2. Target audience: understanding who is experiencing the problem that we are solving and their "pain points".
3. Competition and demand: identifying the competition and market saturation.
4. Distribution: choosing the channels through which we will place our solution on the market.

A comprehensive market analysis serves as the cornerstone of the Go-to-Market Strategy, offering a nuanced exploration of the result's position and latent market potential. To this end, a multifaceted approach is undertaken to glean invaluable insights:

- **Market Definition and Profiling:** A meticulous endeavor is pursued to ascertain and refine the contours of the market to be engaged. This encompasses a panoramic canvassing of customer demographics, underpinned by an intricate comprehension of the prevailing political, societal, and economic fabric. This data mosaic serves as a compass, charting the course of strategic alignment.
- **Problem Statement and Solution Alignment:** The market's challenges are rigorously distilled, articulating the bedrock problematics that reverberate within the target landscape. A crystalline exposition of how the result operates as an antidote to these challenges is meticulously elaborated. This synthesis not only amplifies the solution's relevance but also illuminates its transformative potential.
- **Competitor Landscape Dissection:** The competitive panorama undergoes an exhaustive dissection. This entails identifying not only direct competitors but also analogous products or services seeking to address similar predicaments. Scrutinizing these contenders, their strengths, weaknesses, and modus operandi unfurl. This illumination catalyzes a proactive approach to differentiation and strategic positioning.
- **Customer Aspirations and Feature Fabrication:** The market analysis delves into the psyche of the customer base, decoding their aspirations and the resonant features that kindle their interest. By deciphering their expectations, the result's feature set undergoes a meticulous chiseling. These features are meticulously tailored to mirror the pulse of customer needs, establishing a bridge of symbiotic resonance.

In summation, the market analysis serves as a dynamic compass that delineates the strategic trajectory. By meticulously defining and profiling the market, aligning the solution to its challenges, dissecting the competitive panorama, and weaving a tapestry of customer aspirations into feature embodiment, the analysis bequeaths a robust foundation for strategic orchestration. This orchestration, predicated on discerning insights and foresight, endeavors to navigate the market's nuances with precision, resonance, and strategic dexterity.

During the proposal writing phase, a brief Market Analysis had been conducted, constituting the basis for a more detailed and in-depth analysis. Currently, at this stage, building upon the already existing Market Analysis of

6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

project's previous phase, a more thorough Market Analysis has been set for elaboration, consisting of the preliminary chapters: a) Industry description and outlook, b) Definition and analysis of the target markets', c) Development (market trends, drivers and restraints), e) Market breakup by geographic areas, technology type, end users/industry, etc., f) Competitive landscape analysis, g) Regulation and policy and h) Smart Droplets market potential, paving the way for identifying the market opportunities for each individual commercial Smart Droplets KER. The overall purpose of conducting market analysis per KER lies with the need of developing Go-to-market-strategy for each individual commercial KER.

For the facilitation of the Market Analysis processes a series of the following strategic analysis tools will be utilised and which their templates can be found in Annex P:

- **SWOT analysis:** Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats based on the key issues the result is addressing.
- **PESTLE analysis:** Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors
- **TOWS analysis:** Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats matching them up to create action plans, combining internal and external factors to generate strategic options.

5.3.2.2. Value Chain Network analysis

Considering value chain network analysis as an exploitation pathway for Smart Droplets KERs (Key Exploitable Results) holds immense importance. Bearing in mind the UVP that its individual KER holds, the importance of the value chain network analysis is beyond profound. This approach goes beyond traditional business models by looking closely at how different players, resources, and processes work together in the value chain ecosystem. By using the Value Chain Network Knowledge and Innovation Toolkit (Value Chain Network KIT), we can gain valuable insights.

The Value Chain Network KIT helps us understand how value is created, where there might be challenges, and where opportunities for collaboration lie. It's like having a map that guides us through the complexities of working together effectively. This approach is significant because it lets us make the most of resources, find new ways to work together, and position our offerings better in the market.

When we blend the Smart Droplets KERs into this approach, we can find specific spots where they can create the most impact. This integration allows us to connect with the various players in the ecosystem and tap into the existing value streams. This not only helps us make the most of our KERs but also strengthens the relationships among all the partners involved. Ultimately, this way of thinking helps us create a win-win situation where everyone benefits and grows together.

The implementation of a value chain network for each Key Exploitable Result (KER) is driven by a fundamental need to amplify the effectiveness of our strategic approach. Each KER represents a distinct facet of our project's innovation, and by delving into its individual value chain network, we unlock tailored insights that are indispensable for success.

By dissecting the value chain network specific to each KER, we gain a granular understanding of how it fits into the broader ecosystem. This means recognizing the unique players, resources, and processes that revolve around each KER. Such a targeted analysis enables us to pinpoint precisely how and where the KER generates value within this intricate web of interactions.

Furthermore, this approach empowers us to identify potential bottlenecks, optimize the flow of value, and identify untapped collaborative opportunities. It's akin to having a focused spotlight that illuminates the KER's journey from inception to end-user impact, enhancing our ability to streamline processes and align our strategies effectively.

In essence, implementing a value chain network per KER is about harnessing a tailored lens that enhances our grasp of each KER's distinct value proposition within the larger context. This strategic clarity propels us towards optimal outcomes by ensuring that every KER is not just a standalone innovation, but an integral part of a seamlessly functioning and mutually beneficial ecosystem.

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5.3.2.3. Lean Business Models

Moving on, another exploitation pathway of significant importance is no other than the development of Lean Business Models. The Lean business model reflect in making continuous improvements to business operations and implementing processes that result in optimum business efficiency. The desired results are reached by removing ineffective processes, identifying and eliminating unprofitable products, and improving team productivity. As imprinted in the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5), Lean business model constitute a final visualization of organization's business concept that includes fundamental elements of a business. These activities will be executed in close collaboration with Project Partners. As foreseen within the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5), seven individual Lean Business Models shall be developed for each individual Smart Droplets Commercial KER.

For the preparation and development of the lean business models, the Business model canvas holds a pivotal role, while being an indivisible tool for high – impact customised lean business models per KER. The business model canvas (Annex Q) offers a single page visualisation of the path to commercialization and defines several key components including:

- Key partners who will be responsible for the creation and exploitation of the result
- Key activities required by the value proposition.
- Key resources needed including human, physical, intellectual, financial.
- Value proposition describing - The value of the result - The problem that is being addressed - The specifics of the product being offered. - Which customer needs are being met?
- Customer relationships expected to be established, delivered, and maintained with end users, which ones already exist and at what associated costs.
- Distribution channels that work best, are preferred by customers and are cost-efficient.
- Customer segments the results are targeting, who are the most important customers.
- Cost structure, including the most important costs, the most expensive resource, and activities and whether the outcome is cost-driven or value-driven.
- Revenue streams, what values customers are willing to pay, what do they currently pay, what are the possible streams (e.g., product, subscription fee, usage fee).

5.3.2.4. Funding analysis

The financial projection analysis emerges as a pivotal exploitation pathway for the commercial Smart Droplets Key Exploitable Results (KERs), complementing our strategic framework. This endeavor is underscored by the meticulous mapping of the investment landscape, orchestrated with the primary objective of fortifying project beneficiaries in their pursuit of securing funds pivotal for the sustained viability of their business ventures. The schematic representation encapsulated below delineates our methodological trajectory, encompassing a series of strategic steps dedicated to addressing funding-related imperatives.

Figure 79: Methodology for funding opportunities exploration

This comprehensive exercise encompasses the systematic identification and exploration of diverse funding opportunities spanning both public and private domains. The aim is to empower Smart Droplets beneficiaries to access follow-up investments that galvanize the financial longevity of their entrepreneurial undertakings. Our findings gleaned from this proactive exploration will interweave with the organization's financial plan in congruence with the realm of its key exploitable results.

This financial plan delves into a meticulous review of the cost structure and revenue streams, bolstered by the prospects of complementary fundraising avenues identified through the funding opportunities exploration. The financial projection analysis marries these intricate elements with the overarching insights drawn from meticulous market research and the multifaceted pursuit of funding prospects.

In essence, the financial projection analysis unifies strategic foresight, funding exploration, and the organization's financial trajectory, charting an enriched course that fortifies the Smart Droplets KERs' journey towards financial sustainability. It is a dynamic compass that navigates the intricate terrain of securing essential funds, ensuring not only the vitality of the KERs but also the enduring success of the associated business solutions.

5.4. IPR Strategy

This chapter, building upon the dedicated Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5) developed in the previous months (M6), expanding the preliminary results, as presented in the Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1), illustrates the IPR Strategy, as described in the abovementioned deliverables, as well as the IPR Strategy Actions implemented so far.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) encompass ownership privileges pertaining to products of intellectual creation, including innovations, names, visual representations, and designs. These rights empower creators to reap financial gains from their conceptualizations. Achieving a delicate equilibrium between the interests of creators and the general public can significantly cultivate an environment conducive to ingenuity and advancement.

Each of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) harbors the potential for involvement in IPR management. The meticulous blueprint delineated in the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5), will furnish a comprehensive strategy for each result, delineating tangible steps that partners must undertake in relation to IPR. Smart Droplets will conduct a thorough assessment of protective measures required for any result that stands to be commercially or industrially exploited. Subsequently, these evaluations will inform discerning decisions regarding the safeguarding of these assets, contingent upon considerations of feasibility, reasonability, and legitimacy.

Following the IPR Methodology (Figure 80) as depicted in Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5), up to this point the first two stages, namely Proposal Stage and Grant Preparation Phase, reflecting Background IP and Consortium Agreement, accordingly, have been completed. Building upon the IPR extends described within the first two phases of the IPR Methodology, Smart Droplets is currently following the Project Implementation Phase of the IPR Strategy.

Figure 80: Smart Droplets' IPR Methodology

The accomplished strides of the preceding stages have seamlessly ushered us into the Project Implementation Phase of the IPR Strategy. From the very inception during the Project Planning and Proposal Stage, meticulous

6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

considerations were devoted to every participant's background, tangible and intangible assets, alongside the potential IPRs that they encompassed. This foresight ensured that the foundation was meticulously laid to harness these assets for the project's advancement and the anticipated utilization of IPR-bound outcomes. The aggregation of pivotal assets of interest has culminated in the formulation of the Preliminary Results Ownership List.

As we transition into the realm of Grant Preparation, the multifaceted facets pertaining to knowledge management and IPR administration have been meticulously addressed, encapsulated within the robust Consortium Agreement (CA). This document rigorously defines intricate aspects encompassing confidentiality, the landscape of Background & Sideground Intellectual Property (IP), ownership dynamics, legal safeguards for results, avenues for result exploitation, and access rights. Within this construct, the principle of Results Ownership stands paramount, where each participating entity retains ownership over the results it contributes. Additionally, in scenarios of collaborative result generation, the mechanism of Joint Ownership prevails. Under this, partners involved collaboratively delineate their respective contributions, subsequently cementing these delineations through a Joint Ownership agreement. This accord paves the path for future exploitation endeavors, poised on a foundation of equitable cooperation and strategic foresight.

In the context of the Project Implementation Phase of the IPR Strategy, a series of actions and activities have been elaborated, as foreseen. More precisely, a preliminary work towards formulating the basic concepts of IP and IPR has been conducted. A dedicated workshop targeting Smart Droplets Partners is foreseen as mentioned in the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5) and scheduled for November 2023 (M15), acting as an Introduction to IPR tool. Actions have been elaborated for the development of IP Workshop's content, as follows:

IP Workshop Content

The IP Workshop acting as an Introduction to IPR tool, aims at increasing the familiarity readiness level of the consortium with the IPR and IP concepts. More specifically, with reference to the content of the workshop, it shall entail:

IPR Thematics:

- Intellectual Property Concepts and Definitions on Strategic Level.
- Main Intellectual Property Issues & Concepts.
- Legal Environment of Horizon Europe.

Types of IPR:

The standard forms of IPR protection include:

- **Patent:** an exclusive right granted for an invention. It allows the owner to decide how and whether the invention can be used by others.
- **Trademark:** a sign that distinguishes goods and services of one enterprise from those of another
- **Industrial design:** includes the aesthetic aspect of an object. 2D features can include patterns, lines, and colours, whereas 3D features extend to shape and surface.
- **Copyright:** is the legal term to describe the rights over literary and artistic work but can also extend to databases, advertisement, maps, and technical drawings
- **Trade-secret:** commercially valuable confidential information which may be sold or licensed. This can include technical or nontechnical data, formulas, patterns, methods, lists of customers.
- **Confidentiality:** information that is not publicly known and warrants protection. The choice of the most suitable form will be based upon the specifications of the activity and its results.

The importance of identifying and understanding all standard types of IPR as an enabler for informed decision making regarding IPR strategies will be highlighted within the Workshop. Finally, dedicated time will be allocated, during the workshop, in showcasing the fundamental aspects and specifications, based on which the choice of the most suitable form/ type of IPR is made.

5.5. Next Steps

Smart Droplets' demonstration planning is divided into the following three phases, reflecting the project's pilot phases, based on the agile scrum concept of minimum viable product (MVP):

- *Design & Plan, MVP1: covering from the project's start date (M0) up to December 2023 (M16)*
- *Field deployment, MVP2: covering from December 2023 (M16) up to December 2024 (M28)*
- *Field deployment & holistic evaluation, MVP3: covering from December 2024 (M28) up to February 2026 (M42).*

Considering that the timeframe for the Exploitation Pathways progression shall reflect, in a way, the timelines of project's activities, as imprinted in the Sustainability, Scalability & IPR management strategy v1 (D6.5) the Exploitation and Sustainability activities timeline aligns with the three MVP Phases of project's demonstration planning.

After having described the activities and actions elaborated so far, in the context of the Exploitation Pathways and IPR Management, the following steps are foreseen for the up-and-coming months, and up the next updated version 3 of the respective deliverable, classified into the two first MVP phases.

Next Steps - Design & Plan, MVP1 phase

Within the MVP1 Phase, following the preparation of the Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue template, which has already been developed, the Workshop #1 is foreseen to be conducted in November 2023 (M15), where the overarching Exploitation and Sustainability strategy will be presented to the consortium, encompassing comprehensive guidance on how to effectively populate The Catalogue. Moreover, within the Workshop #1 the validation of the initial version of the Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue will take place and as a consequence, the validation of the seven identified KERs, included in the Catalogue. Final subject of the Workshop #1 will be the presentation and explanation of the methodology for the identification and inclusion of new non-commercial KERs, based on which the Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue shall be finetuned one more time, granting project partners the opportunity to refine and augment the Exploitation and IP Catalogue, encompassing nuanced descriptions of commercial project outcomes and the potential inclusion of emerging non-commercial KERs, by the end of the MVP1 Phase. Following, other activities of paramount importance, which shall be expected within the MVP1 Phase rest with update of the already existing from the proposal phase Market Analysis, abided by its customisation per each individual KER, concluding on seven (7) individual Market Analysis dedicated to each individual Smart Droplet Result. Concomitantly, the inception of the first IP workshop transpires, dedicated to presenting rudimentary IP considerations to project partners. Finally, from September 2023 (M13), Smart Droplets Exploitation pathways shifts towards meticulously mapping funding opportunities. This endeavour aims to bolster project beneficiaries in their quest for funding that buttresses the financial sustainability of their business solutions. The resultant insights will be shared with the consortium in the dedicated Funding workshop, by the end of the MVP1 Phase.

Next Steps - Field deployment, MVP2 phase

The MVP2 Phase, which is signified with the start of the year 2024 (M17) consists of a series of foreseen activities which enable the Exploitation Pathways of Smart Droplets Results. Upon submitting D6.6 in M18, preparations ensue for D6.7, delineating findings from activities tied to joint exploitation plan preparation. Workshop A brings forth collaborative discussions on co-creating joint asset business cases, formulating optimal business models, navigating organizational structures for commercialization, and addressing IPR considerations. In Workshop B, all project partners convene anew to collectively generate Lean Canvas for joint assets, while contemplating marketing entry strategies and associated risks. This phase also marks the commencement of an initial analysis of viable exploitation avenues for non-commercial results featured in the Exploitation and IP Catalogue. To underscore the long-term viability of our joint exploitation plan(s), a financial analysis is conducted, offering forecasts for the assets' initial commercialization years. D6.7 culminates in an updated iteration of the Exploitation and IP Catalogue, poised to serve as a steadfast tool for the consistent monitoring of the project's exploitable outcomes.

6. Conclusions

The respective document Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2 (D6.2) constitutes a sequel of the initial Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1). Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v1 (D6.1) lays an overview of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation phases during the whole project lifetime. The main objective of the document is to outline the initial DEC plan which will be implemented during the first month of Smart Droplets, while laying out the set of the main communication activities and tools, with guidelines for partners to disseminate and exploit results and reach DEC's KPIs.

In a more comprehensive delineation, this document encapsulates an extensive spectrum of pivotal endeavors while concurrently establishing their chronological cadence. These endeavors coalesce into a meticulously orchestrated symphony, harmonizing the realms of dissemination, communication, and exploitation objectives. As a collective whole, all project stakeholders ardently engage in the orchestration of Smart Droplets' communication and dissemination landscape, embarking upon a shared odyssey to ensure the optimal realization of project outcomes and the maximal amplification of their influence.

The forthcoming Third Plan and Reports for Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation, scheduled for submission at the juncture of M24, shall manifest as an enhanced iteration, iteratively honed from the preceding second rendition – the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan and Reports v2 (D6.2). This imminent iteration bears the mandate to critically assess the current plan, scrutinizing the landscape for prevailing frailties and inherent merits within the employed strategies and tools. Moreover, it will extend its purview to delineate objectives of strategic essence and articulate tangible actions extending beyond the M24 horizon, encompassing the journey until the fourth iteration at M42.

Annex A: Smart Droplets brand book

BRAND GUIDELINES

Color palette

BRAND GUIDELINES

Brand typography

Font name: GEOMETOS ROUNDED

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss
Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

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11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20

FONT NAME: LATO

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss
Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

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11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20

BRAND GUIDELINES

Logo variations

BRAND GUIDELINES

Brand applications

BRAND GUIDELINES

Partners logo

Annex B: Logo Variations

Annex C: Banner for Social Media

Annex D: Deliverable template

Enter your deliverable title here

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Lead Beneficiary	
Work Package	
Deliverable type	
Delivery Date (Dn2)	
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Abstract:	

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Date	Version	Author/Contributor/Reviewer	Summary of main changes

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SRN	Selected, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement		Y
SRN-A	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/1884		Y
SRN-B	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/1884		Y
SRN-C	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/1884		Y
SRN-D	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/1884		Y

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SMART DROPLETS CONSORTIUM				
PARTICIPANT NUMBER	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY	
1	GEOPONIC PANEPYTHION ATHINON	GAIA	GR	
2	WAGeningen UNIVERSITY	WU	NL	
3	FUNDACIO FURCAT	FUT	ES	
4	FONDAZIONE VIGORE LAB	VLF	IT	
5	FOODSCALE HUB BARCELONA ASSOCIATION FOR ANTI-ANTIBIOTIC AND INNOVATION ACTIVI	FSA	GR	
6	AGENCIJA ZA RAZVOJ	ARC	HR	
7	AGENCIJA ZA RAZVOJ	ARC	HR	
8	PETROS ANTONI ETASMA	AGROMA SA	GR	
9	PROYECTO AGRICOLA DE CATALUNYA	FEMAC	ES	

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Project name: Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotics technology
 Project acronym: Smart Droplets
 Topic: HORIZON-CL2-2021-00174 (CORRECTION 01-09)
 Type of action: HORIZON Innovative Actions
 Project starting date: 1 September 2022
 Project duration: 62 months

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	

Table 1: [Add name of the table]

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1. Title 1

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2	6	10
3	7	11
4	8	12
TOTAL	TOTAL	TOTAL

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Figure 1: [Add name of the figure]

Annex E: Brochures

6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

Annex F: Posters

Smart Droplets

SMART DROPLETS TURNING LESS INTO MORE!

- ▶ An environmental, socially responsible, and economically inclusive tech-solution for the overuse of fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture
- ▶ Fast-tracking the EU Green Deal Objectives and targets of 2030
- ▶ Showcasing the sustainable solution with two multi-actor live pilots in complementary yet diverse environments
- ▶ Demonstrating the scalability and success of deep tech solutions on apple orchards and wheat fields.

▶ TECHNOLOGICAL BUILDING BLOCKS FOR NOVEL CROP CARE

<p>DATA INFRASTRUCTURES</p> <p>The digital infrastructure of Smart Droplets will be based on a cloud-based architecture that will allow for the use of big data by farmers.</p>	<p>AI MODELS</p> <p>Smart Droplets will create models for predictive analytics of the field and crop yield, which will be used to optimize crop care.</p>	<p>DIGITAL TWINS</p> <p>Smart Droplets will create a hybrid solution for crop care, combining the use of digital twins, IoT, and AI to optimize crop care.</p>	<p>ROBOTIC SYSTEMS</p> <p>Smart Droplets will create an intelligent system for crop care, capable of translating large amounts of data from the field into meaningful information and applying commands to help farmers, society and the planet.</p>	<p>DIRECT INJECTION SPRAYING DEVICES</p> <p>Smart Droplets will develop and create a complete system and upgrade components to improve the accuracy, efficiency, and safety of the spraying process.</p>
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Follow us and find out more about apple orchards and wheat farms that are leading towards the Green Deal objectives and the next level with AI.

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6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

SMART DROPLETS TURNING LESS INTO MORE!

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Apple Orchard Pilot Facts

Why?
Apples are among the crops where the highest amounts of pesticides are used. Insufficient control measures of apple scabs and other fungal diseases can lead to economic losses.

How?
By automatizing a tractor capable of working 24/7 in order to perform the spraying operations, together with sensors to detect the health of the plant to apply the right kind and amount of fungicides, at the right time, in the right place.

For who?
Farmers, farmers' associations & cooperatives, agronomists & advisors, agri-food technology manufacturers, AI/Data/Robotics providers, AI/Data/Robotics DfEs, Policy Makers & Standardisation Bodies

Where?
The Mediterranean region: Spain

SMART DROPLETS PROJECT EXPECTS TO DECREASE THE WASTE CREATED BY INFECTED AND UNUSABLE APPLES WHILE CREATING BETTER CONDITIONS FOR FARMERS, EUROPE AND THE PLANET!

Follow us and find out more about apple orchards and what farms that are moving towards the Green Deal objectives and the next level with AI, deep tech and robotics systems:

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Wheat Farm Pilot Facts

Why?
Wheat accounts for almost half of the main cereal production in the EU, while weeds can reduce wheat yield by 15%-20% per annum, with nitrogen application needing to be re-evaluated.

How?
By focusing on chemical weeding, nitrogen fertilization and fungicide applications, while utilizing state-of-the-art technologies and especially the most relevant advances in AI/Data/Robotics, Smart Droplets will optimise farm operation working towards the EU Green Deal Targets.

For who?
Farmers, farmers' associations & cooperatives, agronomists & advisors, agri-food technology manufacturers, AI/Data/Robotics providers, AI/Data/Robotics DfEs, Policy Makers & Standardisation Bodies.

Where?
Central Lithuania, Baltic area

SMART DROPLETS PROJECT EXPECTS TO INCREASE YIELDS, DECREASE CHEMICAL USE AND OPERATIONAL COSTS ALL WHILE CREATING BETTER CONDITIONS FOR FARMERS, EUROPE AND THE PLANET!

Follow us and find out more about apple orchards and what farms that are moving towards the Green Deal objectives and the next level with AI, deep tech and robotics systems:

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Annex G: Factsheets

Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotic technologies.

AT A GLANCE

PROJECT TITLE:	Accelerating the achievement of EU Green Deal Goals for pesticide and fertilizer reduction through AI, data and robotic technologies (Smart Droplets)	DURATION:	September 2022 - February 2026 (42 months)
PROGRAMME:	HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-09	COORDINATOR:	Agricultural University of Athens (AUA), Greece
INSTRUMENT:	HORIZON innovation action	CONSORTIUM:	9 Partners from six European countries
TOTAL BUDGET:	€2 998 370,00	SOCIAL MEDIA:	

THE CHALLENGE

Agricultural environments are characterized by **rapid changes**, while crop care tasks have always been **repetitive, tedious, and potentially hazardous**. Consequently, the sector is shifting towards more selective treatment applications to **improve the quality and efficiency of chemical spraying**. To mitigate environmental pollution and de facto negative implication on human health, there is an **urgent need to improve the use of pesticide and fertilizer use**. The EU Green Deal has set ambitious targets to reduce the use of pesticide and fertilizer by 2030, which cannot be reached without the use of **advanced technologies**. AI Data and robotic advances on SFTs (Smart Farming Technologies) can contribute in fulfilling this ambition bringing benefits in terms of **reduced pesticide use, low carbon emissions, low water use, reduced food waste**, thus enabling environmental sustainability.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The Smart Droplets project introduces a novel approach for crop care tasks, by connecting key-technological aspects during open field spraying. Based on the scope of the EU Green Deal and the recently reformed Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), Smart Droplets is committed to advance both hardware and software capabilities during chemical application, in order to meet the sustainability goals. Smart Droplets' solution relies upon critical technological building blocks, that constitute a novel crop care approach through the use of:

- Data infrastructures
- Robotic systems
- AI models
- Digital twins
- Direct Injection Spraying (DIS)

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Annex H: Roll-up Banner

Annex I: Dissemination and Communication Material

Annex J: Zoom Background

Annex K: Press release template

TITTLE PLACE HOLDER

IMAGE

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TITTLE PLACE HOLDER

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TITTLE PLACE HOLDER

PROJECT DETAILS

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TITTLE PLACE HOLDER

IMAGE

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Annex L: Event Planning Template

Smart Droplets SYNERGY MAPPING

Please complete the following form with events that you are already planning on attending over the next 6 months, or any that you are aware of, and feel would be well suited for Smart Droplets participation.

Smart Droplets Event Planning						
#	Name and Type of event	Event link	Date(s) / Location(s)	Scale	Target groups	Potential Data4Food2030 involvement
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						
...						

Annex M: Synergy Mapping Template

Smart Droplets SYNERGY MAPPING

Please complete the following form with projects, initiatives and/or networks that you are involved with or are aware of and that could provide an opportunity for joint activities and collaboration.

Smart Droplets Synergy & Liaison mapping						
#	Type of Initiative	Full name	Website	Initiative Leader	Focus area	Potential joint activities
1						
2						
3						
4						
5						
6						

Annex N: Publication Planning Template

Smart Droplets PUBLICATION PLANNING

Please complete the following form with peer reviewed journal publications, industry magazines, white papers, any other publication you plan to make.

Smart Droplets Publication Planning			
#	Type of publication	Publication website	Estimated submission date
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
6			
...			

Annex O: Template of Smart Droplets Exploitation and IP Catalogue

KERs (Key Exploitable Results)		Scope of exploitation					Target groups [to whom]	Means of exploitation (how)	Linked IPRs to the KERs		
KER no	Please add any other exploitable results if relevant	Scientific	Commercial	Policy making	Training	other (please specify)	For additional KERs please see note for the list of target groups	For additional KERs please describe the means of exploitation.	Please indicate what might be the possible IPRs, where relevant (one KER might be subject to more than one type of IPR)		
									IPR	IPR	if other please specify
		<input type="checkbox"/>									
		<input type="checkbox"/>									
		<input type="checkbox"/>									

Annex P: Strategic analysis tools

PESTLE Factor	Your notes	Potential impact	Implications and Importance			
			Time Frame: Short/Medium/Long	Type: Opportunity/Threat	Implication: Increasing/ Reducing/ Not yet determined	Relative Importance: H = High M = Medium L = Low
	<i>About your organisation and how the factors listed on the left might impact on marketing for your organisation/SBU</i>	<i>H = High M = Medium L = Low U = Undecided</i>				
P Political						
E Economic						
S Sociological						
T Technological						
E Environmental						
L Legal						

6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and reports v2

<p>Internal factors</p> <p>External factors</p>	<p>Strengths (S)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S1. • S2. • S3. • S4. • S5. • S6. • S7. 	<p>Weakness (W)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • W1. • W2. • W3. • W4. • W5. • W6. • W7.
<p>Opportunities (O)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • O1. • O2. • O3. • O4. • O5. • O6. • O7. 	<p>S-O strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S..O.. 	<p>W-O strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • W..O..
<p>Threats (T)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • T1. • T2. • T3. • T4. • T5. • T6. • T7. 	<p>S-T strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S..T.. 	<p>W-T strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • W..T..

Annex Q: Business model canvas

KEY PARTNERS	KEY ACTIVITIES	VALUE PROPOSITIONS	CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS
	KEY RESOURCES		CHANNELS	
COST STRUCTURE			REVENUE STREAMS	